

CEE2ACT

**Empowering the Central and
Eastern European Countries to Develop
Bioeconomy Strategies and Action Plans**

**Baseline assessment report on bioeconomy implementation
and policy development in CEE2ACT target countries**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report attempts to provide a clear picture of the current state of play of the development of the implementation of circular bioeconomy and circular bioeconomy strategies in the CEE2ACT countries including Baltic States.

On the one hand, extended inventories of the implementation of bioeconomy strategies but also on socio-economic and environmental framework are provided to show the status quo in each country. On the other hand, main challenges and potentials have been queried from target country partners. The information is complemented with existing data and knowledge from reports of BIOEASTsUP and dashboards of the EC's Knowledge Centre of Bioeconomy.

The **political background** of the individual countries in CEE2ACT is already very different and this must be taken into account when designing the bioeconomy strategy in each case. Particularly in the countries where implementation is not yet in the preliminary stages, more educational work must be done and it is not enough to work on direct implementation, but the focus must also be placed on the political implementation of the respective strategies.

The **economic framework conditions** are an essential factor for the implementation of bioeconomy. Looking at GDP, turnover or value added at factor costs, target countries tend to have lower values than contributing countries in CEE2ACT.

Bioeconomy related infrastructure is expandable in all countries, starting from increasing the share of renewables for electricity, for heating and cooling to the installation of biowaste management and recycling. There are partly large differences in the theoretically usable potential of biomass in the countries. Whereas the forestry area is dominating in countries such as Sweden, Finland and Slovenia, the arable land is predominant in Hungary, Romania and Poland. Organic farming is an expandable sector when looking at the current share of organic farming that is below 10% in many countries. The potential of accelerating organic farming was also recognised by experts in target countries.

Considering the **environmental health** of countries, it can be noticed that some still have elevated pollution levels in water bodies. Even more than 25% of rivers (Biological Oxygen Demand of above 4 mg (O₂) per l) are affected in many countries. This is a clear target for action. Also, the lack of organic matter in soil is recognised as a major problem. A loss of soil organic matter is forecasted for around 30% of the European area under current land management practices, especially in the Southern part of Europe. Especially countries with high share of livestock farming should focus to utilise the manure for energy and for fertilizing. This was also recognised and reported by experts.

Key bioeconomy sectors are agriculture and forestry as well as the food production sector. This can be observed with the turnover (Food, Beverage and Tobacco have an

average contribution of 41% to the turnover of all bioeconomy related sectors) and the focus that implemented initiatives have as well as reported challenges and potentials. Biomass utilization, so to say the supply-side, has strong focus in current development. However, also the demand-side is important to keep the loop in the bioeconomy. Untapped potential in biomass supply needs to be accelerated but certainly the demand-side shall also be focused and supported by political implementation, investment, collaboration and research. The potential for biomass for energy (e.g. biogas production) is largely recognized, but there is still potential to enlarge biomass utilization for materials. The transformation to a bio-based industry is often hindered due to financial and knowledge barriers.

Collaborations can target to foster communication between stakeholders, eliminate barriers, and replicate best practices, so that bioeconomy will move from a broad EU framework to a successful implementation in practice. CEE2ACT will certainly help to path this way.

DISCLAIMER

The CEE2ACT project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. Introduction

Bioeconomy is implemented in CEE2ACT countries in different ways and to a different extent. Whereas in some countries, the bioeconomy has already been implemented in form of a national strategy, action plan and related policies, in some others the bioeconomy strategies/action plans and related policies are in process of development while in some implementation of bioeconomy concept have not been developed.

The aim of this report is to provide a comprehensive inventory of the current status of bioeconomy implementation across all partner countries including the Baltic States. The following components are mapped and illustrated for each country and for all countries in comparison:

- Bioeconomy POLICY LANDSCAPE
- Bioeconomy related INFRASTRUCTURE
- Bioeconomy ECOSYSTEM CONDITIONS
- Bioeconomy INITIATIVES
- Challenges and Potentials of bioeconomy implementation

In addition to the components, it was necessary to define the term “bioeconomy” at project level.

The inventory of the current status shall reveal environmental challenges and a list of key bioeconomy sectors for the CEE2ACT target countries, that is the basis for the definition of sustainability criteria and performance indicators (Task 2.2).

1.1 Method

This deliverable shall serve as a knowledge base for the current status of countries involved in CEE2ACT including the Baltic States. For the collection of the information and data the following approaches and data sources were used (Table 1):

- A) Desktop research to investigate on existing information
- B) Survey among experts within the CEE2ACT consortium
- C) Information extracted from the documents prepared (e.g. Concept Papers, report 1.2, 1.4) as part of the BIOEASTsUP project (H2020)

Table 1: Data sources and level of information

Existing information	Expert knowledge	Other
Data was gathered from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System dashboard • EU Bioeconomy Country Dashboard • JRC Reports (Giuntoli et al., 2020; Mubareka et al., 2023) • EUROSTAT • Worldbank 	Experts from target countries were asked on the following topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation status of their National Bioeconomy Strategy • Sectors covered/pinpointed in the Bioeconomy strategy, if any. • EU policies and programs related to bioeconomy • Collaboration initiatives • Challenges and potentials 	Concept papers, reports T1.2, T1.4 and Strategic and Research Innovation Agenda (SRIA) from BIOEASTsUP project (H2020) were reviewed to use already identified information from different countries with special focus on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges and potentials

The latest available data from the **European Commission’s Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy** are used to outline the situation in the CEE2ACT countries. The EU Bioeconomy Country Dashboard (European Commission, 2023a) and the dedicated JRC reports (e.g., Mubareka et al. 2023; Giuntoli et al. 2020) publish current, and informative data and information for many EU- countries. Data was extracted for CEE2ACT countries including the Baltic States and processed to illustrate them for each country and for all countries in comparison. For the comparisons, absolute values were processed into relative ones (e.g. per capita, in % of). Data points that were selected are shown in the Annex 7.1.

The status was illustrated by each component and interpreted to draw conclusions for the assessment in CEE2ACT.

The **expertise** within the consortium was used to fill data and knowledge gaps. A survey was conducted to collect information directly from partners in target countries. The survey is shown in the Annex 7.2. As Serbia is not included in the EU Bioeconomy Dashboard, experts from Serbia provided links to dedicated databases. Although a lot of data is available from Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, it is though hardly possible to include this data in the existing statistics related to EU Bioeconomy Dashboard without knowing the details of the methodology of estimating bioeconomy related indicators. Where applicable the information on Serbia was included in the text.

The Central-Eastern European Initiative for Knowledge-based Agriculture, Aquaculture and Forestry in the Bioeconomy (**BIOEAST**) –shared strategic research and innovation framework for working towards sustainable bioeconomies in the Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries: Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Croatia, Hungary, Lithuania, Latvia,

Poland, Romania, Slovenia and Slovakia. Concept paper have been developed, but unfortunately not all of them have been published until the deployment of this report. So, only key outcomes such as main challenges and potentials could have been extracted with the help of partners (IUNG) that were mainly involved in BIOEASTsUP project.

Considering the existing regional knowledge and network in the Baltic States, CEE2ACT also includes studies of best practises and policy analyses in the Baltic States as part of the activities.

1.2 CEE2ACT countries

Bioeconomy is implemented to a varying extent in the different countries. This is also the case in the countries involved in CEE2ACT (CEE2ACT countries). Countries, that have already a national bioeconomy strategy in place are called “contributing countries” and countries, that have no existing strategy or one in development are called “target countries”. As there is existing knowledge and a good network in the Baltic States, those countries are considered as well. The used acronyms for each country are shown in the table below.

Table 2: Countries involved in CEE2ACT including Baltic States

CEE2ACT “contributing countries”	CEE2ACT “target countries”	Baltic States
AT Austria BE Belgium DE Germany ES Spain FI Finland NL Netherlands SE Sweden	BG Bulgaria* CZ Czech Republic* GR Greece HR Croatia* HU Hungary* PL Poland* RO Romania* RS Serbia SI Slovenia* SK Slovak Republic*	EE Estonia* LT Latvia* LV Lithuania*

*BIOEAST Countries

2. CEE2ACT Definition of “Bioeconomy”

The term “bioeconomy” was defined at project level to enable a clear and common understanding of the scope. The definition at project level aimed to be more specific than the existing ones. Each country should use the same scope and vocabulary within the project. It was observed during partner meetings that this is very essential in the further project work.

The definition of “bioeconomy” at project level was agreed to be based on the EU definition (European Commission, 2018) and complemented by additional resources, sectors and principles (BOKU, 2023) to narrow down the scope:

Definition of bioeconomy at project level (long description)

Bioeconomy at project level shall include and interlink:

- land and marine ecosystems and the services they provide;
- all primary production sectors that use and produce biological resources (agriculture, forestry, fisheries, and aquaculture) and other sources (insects, algae, yeasts, fungi, microorganism etc.)
- and all economic and industrial sectors that use biological resources and processes to produce food, feed, bio-based products, energy and services.

This involves not only the extraction of renewable raw materials (Principle 1: the avoidance of fossil carbon sources and scarce, non-renewable raw materials) but also the utilisation of biogenic waste and residues (Principle 2: the circular orientation) in a sustainable way (Principle 3: the recognition of ecological and social framework conditions).

Systems and principles mentioned in the definition as well as relevant sectors are illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 1: Systems and principles of bioeconomy (project definition)

Definition of bioeconomy at project level (short description)

According to Figure 1 within CEE2ACT bioeconomy refers to an economy that relies on renewable, natural resources from all parts of ecosphere in a sustainable manner to produce food and feed, pulp and paper, wood and wood products, as well as other biobased products and bioenergy (incl. biofuels) including the circular use of organic residues and waste. Ecosystem services are part of the bioeconomy.

3. Status of bioeconomy implementation in CEE2ACT countries

3.1 Bioeconomy policy landscape

3.1.1 National bioeconomy strategy

The status of the national bioeconomy strategies of the CEE2ACT countries including the Baltic States is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Status of national bioeconomy strategies in the CEE2ACT countries incl. Baltic states as of February 2023 (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023a; Blank map of Europe.svg by Maix ([https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Blank_map_of_Europe_\(with_disputed_regions\).svg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Blank_map_of_Europe_(with_disputed_regions).svg)))

All of the **target countries** agree with the status communicated at the EC's Dashboard and explained their status in more detail.

More specifically, experts of Bulgaria (**BG**) reported that at the moment it lacks both a comprehensive policy and national strategic documents related to bioeconomy, developed on the basis of relevant analyses. There are separate sectoral and regional strategies, but they do not contribute to the overall solution of the problem and do not sufficiently support the development of the bioeconomy in terms of technology, resources and ecology. From the beginning of 2023, under the BIOEASTsUP project, a draft Strategy for the Development of the Bioeconomy in Bulgaria 2023-2030 was developed by Agricultural academy, which does not meet the requirements of the methodology of the Council of Ministers for the development, public discussion and adoption of strategic documents in Bulgaria.

The experts from the **CZ** stated The Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic has supported the implementation of bioeconomy and was part of the BIOEAST initiative from the very beginning. In July 2019, the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic was the only one to prepare a Bioeconomy Concept for the Czech Republic from the perspective of the Ministry of Agriculture for the years 2019-2024, which considers the bioeconomy as one of its key priorities. The Concept Paper of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic aims to support the development of the bioeconomy to ensure sustainable management of natural resources, sustainable agriculture, forestry, water management and aquaculture, sustainable production of food and feed, and strengthening the role of primary producers and their integration into the bioeconomy value chain, as well as on the forestry side the involvement of the entire value chain of downstream sectors. At the beginning of September 2022, the Government of the Czech Republic approved the Research Concept of the Ministry of Agriculture 2023+, one of the key areas (or one of the three horizontal areas) is bioeconomy.

Experts from Greece (**GR**) indicated that there is no formal national strategy for the bioeconomy, other energy and climate change plans/programmes related to the bioeconomy have been developed. Greece, unlike the other countries, is in a phase of transition and decarbonisation. It is solving its energy problem. The strategies related to the bioeconomy have been delivered. The next step will be the national strategy for the bioeconomy.

The experts from Hungary (**HU**) stated that the Ministry of Agriculture as a core member of BIOEAST Initiative has just published (31 March 2023) the elaboration of a strategical bioeconomy concept paper in the framework of BIOEASTsUP project (2019-2023). The main aim of this document is to serve as a basis for cross-sectoral and multidisciplinary dialogue on sustainability issues of biomass related sectors. The introduction of the concept paper for interested parties (e.g. universities, firms, farmers, investors, representatives of different bio-based sectors etc.) has started (several in-person and online workshops, info-days (like CBE JU Infoday 26 Apr 2023). Also there is a close cooperation with the organizers of Circular Economy Technology Platform (CETP) –

Circular Hungary and the Prime Minister Office who was responsible for the elaboration of the CE national strategy with the methodological support of OECD. The CE strategy was introduced to the wider public in March of 2023. One of the main focuses is on the circularity of biomass besides the construction waste and plastics. The development of bioeconomy strategy is now at the stage of capacity building of existing supporters, widening the circle of new supporters, organizing meetings with the involvement of old and potential new bioeconomy players in order to define the national level priorities.

Polish experts (PL) reported that beside developing a strategy, Poland has developed a 'concept paper' as part of the BIOEASTsUP project (summary is available here: <https://bioeast.eu/download/pl-concept-paper-summary/>) that may contribute to the development of a bioeconomy strategy. The experts pointed out that Poland has several documents that take into account elements of the bioeconomy (e.g. the roadmap for the transition towards a closed loop economy). There are also several cross-sectoral initiatives that support the development of the bioeconomy (e.g. 'Cooperation agreement for the development of the biogas and biomethane sector'). In addition, strategies (in certain regions - e.g. the Mazovian Region) for bioeconomy development are in operation at regional level or its elements are included in Regional Innovation Strategies.

Experts from Romania (RO) noted that Romania participated in the BIOEASTsUP project, where a concept paper has been developed. Additionally, seven regions (NUTS 2) have published strategies related to the bioeconomy: one region with a fully dedicated bioeconomy strategy, two regions have a strategy with a strong bioeconomy focus (other related strategy) and four regions have strategies with minimum bioeconomy content (other related strategy). One region (NUTS 3) published a bioeconomy roadmap within the framework of the BE-Rural project (RO123).

Data on the bioeconomy status in Serbia (RS) are not available on the EU Bioeconomy Country Dashboard. Experts stated that currently no National Bioeconomy Strategy exists in RS, but there is the Roadmap for Circular economy and the concept of circular economy is analysed and elaborated through four National strategies (Agriculture and Rural Development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2014-2024, Sustainable urban development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia until 2030, Industrial Policy Strategy of the Republic of Serbia from 2021 to 2030, Smart specialisation Strategy of the Republic of Serbia 2020 – 2027) and two National programs (Circular Economy Development Programme in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2022 to 2024 and Waste management Program in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2022–2031)

Experts from Slovakia (SK) stated that there is no dedicated National Bioeconomy Strategy in Slovakia. However, the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic is currently working on the Roadmap for Circular Bioeconomy.

Sectors included in the strategy

Generally, all sectors related to bioeconomy are included in existing national strategies except for some country specific conditions (e.g. Austrian strategy doesn't include Fisheries because of its minor relevance in Austria) and is foreseen to be included in national strategies under development. Of course, some sectors are pinpointed and some are not depending on the country's settings.

Experts from the Czech Republic (**CZ**) reported that Agriculture and Forestry are pinpointed in their strategy. Also, Romania (**RO**) highlighted 'organic farming' as a major component in the Agricultural sector and 'short agri-food' for Food sector as well as 'bioenergy (from residual biomass)' in the Bioenergy sector. Experts from Slovakia (**SK**) mentioned 'carbon agriculture' as a major field in their planned strategy. Related to polish concept paper (**PL**) the main focus is on developing niche sectors of bioeconomy as: biogas and biomethane, organic farming (agriculture), aquaculture (inland fisheries) and 'short agri-food value chains'.

3.1.2 Other related strategies

The European Green Deal (EGD) (EC 2019) launched by the European Commission in 2019 aims to "transform the EU into a modern, resource, efficient and competitive economy, where there are no net emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050, economic growth is decoupled from resource use and no person and no place is left behind." A wave of initiatives and policies have been introduced to foster bioeconomy as a major component for the implementation of the EGD.

Policies that address or influence the bioeconomy system are among others (Mubareka et al., 2023):

- Common Agricultural Policy
- Forest Strategy
- Policy on Fishery and Aquaculture
- Biodiversity Strategy
- Strategies on Emission Reduction and Climate Protection
- Renewable Energy Directive
- Farm to fork Strategy
- Blue economy approach
- Circular Economy Action Plan
- Industry Strategy
- EU policy framework on biobased, biodegradable and compostable plastics
- Long-term Vision for the EU's Rural Areas
- EU strategy to reduce methane emissions
- Chemicals Strategy

Around 105 strategies were identified by experts in target countries that can be related to bioeconomy. Strategies listed in the EU Dashboard (in total 85 for target countries)

complement the list in the tables shown in the Annex. The strategies were grouped in different categories, each of them related to a specific topic of bioeconomy. As Baltic countries are already included in Mubareka et al. (2023), the focus in this inventory is laid on CEE2ACT target countries, where experts from each country provided the information.

Table 3 gives an overview on the implementation of European strategies and initiatives in target CEE2ACT partner countries. Titles and references to the strategies are listed in Table 4 to Table 18.

Table 3: Strategies related to bioeconomy identified by target country

	Agriculture	Forestry	Climate//Zero Emission Energy	Circular Economy	Industry Strategy	Biodiversity Strategies	Renewable Energy Dir.	Rural Development	Farm to Fork Strategy	Environmental Policy	Blue Economy Strategy	Fisheries/Aquaculture	Biobased Industries
BG Bulgaria*	x	x	x	x	SME	x	x	x	x		x		x
PL Poland*	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	
HU Hungary*	x	x	x	x	food		x	x	x	x		x	
GR Greece	x	x	x	x	x	x		x					
RS Serbia	x	x	x	x	x	x	x						
SK Slovak Republic*	x	x	x	x	x	x	x						
CZ Czech Republic*	x	x	x	x				x		x			
SI Slovenia*	x	x	x	x	x						x		
RO Romania*	x	x	x	x	x								
HR Croatia*	x	x	x	x									

Concerning **Agriculture** all target EU member countries already have an approved Strategic Plan on the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). In Serbia also an Agriculture and Rural Development Strategy is existing. Similar is the situation concerning **forestry** policies which have been implemented in all target countries.

Two of the target countries mention national implementation Strategies on **Fisheries or Aquaculture**. This is the National Fisheries Strategic Plan of HU and the Strategy for the Development of Aquaculture for 2021-2027 in PL. Two other countries (BG and SI deal with the Blue Economy strategy.

Strategies or roadmaps for the transition to a **Circular Economy** have been implemented in all target countries except Croatia, where no information on such dedicated strategy, roadmap or action plan is available. But also, in Croatia a Waste Management Plan is existing.

In the area of **climate**, not least with regard to **reduced emissions** and renewable energy, strategies or plans could also be found in all partner countries. The National Energy and Climate (ENCP) Plan is a ten-year integrated document mandated by the

European Union to each of its member states in order for the EU to meet its overall greenhouse gases emissions targets. It is in force in all EU member target countries, in Serbia the INECP is prepared. Furthermore, no recent documents relating to the newest development in the **Renewable Energy Directive** (RED III) were reported. In half of the target countries, however, National Action Plans for energy from renewable sources is available.

From the main European strategies being connected to the goals of the bioeconomy strategy the **Farm to Fork** strategy turned out to be the least implemented. Only experts from three countries (BG, HU, PL) provided information on this topic.

Also the current EU's **industrial strategy**, as updated in May 2021, refers to different objectives, including resilience, competitive sustainability and the twin transition to a green and digital economy supports the implementation of bioeconomy. Experts from six countries reported the implementation of according strategies in their countries. For HU and BG it turned out that at least the content of this strategy is partly implemented, focusing on SEMs or food industry only.

Strategies on Biodiversity have been implemented in half of the CEE2ACT target countries (BG, GR, PL, RS, SK) and explicit strategies or policies on Environment have only been reported from CZ, HU and PL.

Since not all countries have direct access to the sea the blue economy strategy is not equally implemented. Only BG and SI implemented a Blue Economy Strategies for their countries.

Beside those strategies also other initiatives and programmes are relevant in terms of bioeconomy and have been investigated on their implementation in target partner countries For two countries activities concerning the **chemicals Strategy** for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment have been reported. There is the National Action Plan for the Persistent organic Pollutants in Bulgaria 2020-2030 or in PL where a strategy is in preparation. Concerning **biobased industries** only for Bulgaria a Handbook of Regional and Local Bio-Based Economies was mentioned by the local experts. There was no information from other countries. Biodiversity strategies have been reported from five countries (BG, GR, PL, RS, SK). Strategies on Rural Development have been reported from half of the partner countries.

Table 4: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries - Agriculture

Country	Agriculture
BG	Strategic plan for the development of agriculture and rural areas 2023-2027. Program with goals and activities of the Ministry of Agriculture for 2023.
CZ	Strategy of the Ministry of Agriculture with a view to 2030

	https://eagri.cz/public/web/mze/legislativa/pravni-predpisy-mze/tematicky-prehled/Legislativa-MZe_uplna-zneni_zakon-1997-252-viceoblasti.html https://eagri.cz/public/web/file/713771/SP_SZP_verze_1_3_schvaleno_EK.pdf
GR	STRATEGIC PLAN OF THE COMMON AGRICULTURAL POLICY OF GREECE 2023-2027 (CAP) http://www.minagric.gr/images/stories/docs/agrotis/KAP2023_2027/egkekrimeno_ss_kap_2023_2027.pdf
HU	Rural development programme https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/rural-development/country/hungary_en https://kormany.hu/dokumentumtar/magyarorszag-kap-strategiai-terve-2023-2027
HR	Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plan
PL	Act of 26 January 2023 on financing the common agricultural policy for 2023-2027 https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU202300003322 . Polish Strategic Plan for the Common Agricultural Policy for the years 2023-2027 (CAP) https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/cap-my-country/cap-strategic-plans/approved-csp-0_en?f%5B0%5D=document_country_document_country%3Ahttp%3A//publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/POL https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo/plan-strategiczny-dla-wspolnej-polityki-rolnej-na-lata-2023-27
RO	Strategy for the development of the agri-food sector on average- and long-term 2020-2030 https://www.madr.ro/docs/dezvoltare-rurala/2022/PNS_2023-2027-versiunea_1.2-21.11.2022.pdf
RS	Agriculture and Rural Development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2014-2024. https://uap.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/STRATEGIJA-2014-2020-.pdf
SI	Strategic Plan of the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027 for Slovenia (CAP) https://skp.si/skupna-kmetijska-politika-2023-2027/zakonodaja-skp/zakonodaja
SK	CAP Strategic Plan 2023 - 2027 https://www.mpsr.sk/strategicky-plan-spp-2023-2027/1-43-1327

Table 5: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries - Forestry

Country	Forestry
BG	National strategy for the development of the forestry sector in the Republic of Bulgaria for the period up to 2030. https://www.strategy.bg/PublicConsultations/View.aspx?lang=bg-BG&id=7235
CZ	Concept of the state forestry policy by the year 2035 https://eagri.cz/public/web/file/646382/Koncepcie_statni_lesnicke_politiky_do_roku_2035.pdf
GR	National Forest Strategy, https://ypen.gov.gr/perivallon/dasi/ethniki-stratigiki-gia-ta-dasi/
HU	Forest Strategy https://erdo-mezo.hu/index.php/hirek/olvas/letoltheto-a-nemzeti-erdostrategia-2016-2030-teljes-szovege
HR	National Law on Forests
PL	National Forestry Accounting Plan https://bip.mos.gov.pl/fileadmin/user_upload/bip/strategie_plany_programy/Krajowy_Plan_Rozliczen_dla_L_lesnictwa/NFAP_2019_POLAND_ENG_FINAL.pdf https://bip.mos.gov.pl/strategie-plany-programy/krajowy-plan-rozliczen-dla-lesnictwa/
RO	National Strategy for Forests 2030 http://www.mmediu.ro/app/webroot/uploads/files/HG%20SNP%2004.10.2022%20%20spre%20publicare.do_cx
RS	Forestry development strategy https://upravazasume.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/Strategija-razvoja-sumarstva.pdf

SI	National Forestry Strategy https://www.dnevnik.si/1043020809/objektiv-nova/o-novi-strategiji-eu-na-podrocju-gozdarstva-slovenija-ne-more-sprejemati-novih-obvez-in-omejitev
SK	Vision, prognosis and strategy of forestry development in Slovakia https://www.forestportal.sk/odborna-sekcia-i/lesnicka-politika-a-legislativa/narodna-strategia-rozvoja-lesnictva/

Table 6: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Aquaculture and Fisheries

Country	Aquaculture and Fisheries
BG	
CZ	
GR	
HU	NATIONAL FISHERIES STRATEGIC PLAN OF HUNGARY https://www.agrarszektor.hu/allat/20220525/hatalmas-lokest-kaphat-a-magyar-halagazat-itt-az-uj-nemzeti-strategiai-terv-38259
HR	
PL	Akwakultura 2021-2027, Strategic Plan for Fish Farming https://www.gov.pl/attachment/fbf4397c-5159-4aa7-8945-cfc47bc89e5d Strategy for the development of Aquaculture for 2021-2027 https://bibliotekanauki.pl/articles/2172297
RO	
RS	
SI	
SK	

Table 7: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Biobased industry

Country	Biobased industry
BG	Handbook of Regional and Local Bio-Based Economies, 2020.
CZ	
GR	
HU	
HR	
PL	
RO	
RS	
SI	
SK	

Table 8: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries - Biodiversity

Country	Biodiversity
BG	Strategy for biological diversity in the Republic of Bulgaria, 2022
CZ	
GR	National Biodiversity Strategy & Action Plan, https://ypen.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/legacy/Files/Perivallon/Diaxeirisi%20Fysikoy%20Perivallontos/Biopoikilotita/20200323_ethniki_strathgiki_biodiversity.pdf

HU	
HR	
PL	Biodiversity Strategy 2030 https://www.gov.pl/web/rdos-gorzow-wielkopolski/europejska-strategia-bioroznorodnosci-do-2030-r
RO	
RS	Biodiversity Strategy of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2011 – 2018 https://www.zzps.rs/wp/pdf/strategija_bioloske_raznovrsnosti.pdf
SI	
SK	National biodiversity strategy until 2020 https://www.minzp.sk/ochrana-prirody/medzinarodne-dohovory/dohovor-biodiverzite/aktualizovana-narodna-strategia-ochrany-biodiverzity-do-roku-2020/ Updated strategy on biodiversity protection until 2020

Table 9: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Blue Economy

Country	Blue economy
BG	Black Sea Regional Strategy for Blue Economy and Smart Specialization with Local Action Plans, 2022 Bulgaria: towards the development of the blue economy - December 2020, developed by the World Bank Multi-year National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture in Bulgaria (2021-2027)
CZ	
GR	
HU	
HR	
PL	Strategy for Sustainable Rural, Agricultural and Fisheries Development 2030 (SFDS 2030) (Link) https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo/dokumenty-analzy-szrwir-2030
RO	
RS	
SI	Draft position of the Republic of Slovenia on a new approach for a sustainable blue economy http://vrs-3.vlada.si/MANDAT20/vladnagrada.nsf/71d4985ffda5de89c12572c3003716c4/c74914da44385f05c125871b0044b479?OpenDocument
SK	

Table 10: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries - Chemicals

Country	Chemicals
BG	National Action Plan for the Management of Persistent Organic Pollutants in Bulgaria 2020-2030
CZ	Act No. 350/2011 Coll., on Chemical Substances and Chemical Mixtures and on Amendments to Certain Acts Zákon č. 350/2011 sb., o chemických látkách a chemických směsích a o změně některých zákonů
GR	
HU	
HR	

PL	CSS IN A NUMBER - responsibilities, opportunities and risks arising from the Sustainable Chemicals Strategy https://pipc.org.pl/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/PIPC-Broszura-CSS-online.pdf
RO	
RS	
SI	
SK	

Table 11: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Circular Economy

Country	Circular Economy
BG	Strategy for the transition to a circular economy of the Republic of Bulgaria for the period 2022-2027.
CZ	STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK CIRCULAR ECONOMY OF THE CZECH REPUBLIC 2040 - "A MAXIMUM CIRCULAR CZECH REPUBLIC IN 2040" https://www.dataplan.info/img_upload/7bdb1584e3b8a53d337518d988763f8d/cirkularni-cesko_2040_1.pdf
GR	Circular Economy Greece's new action plan, https://ypen.gov.gr/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/NEO_SXEDIO_DRASIS_KUKLIKH_OIKONOMIA.pdf Law 4685/2020, Article 97. End of the use of plastic bags, https://www.taxheaven.gr/law/4685/2020 "
HU	Towards a National Circular Economy Strategy for Hungary https://www.oecd.org/environment/waste/circular-economy-country-studies.htm
HR	Waste Management Plan of the Republic of Croatia for the period 2017–2022 (OG 3/17, 1/22)
PL	ROAD MAP towards the Transition to Circular Economy https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/sites/default/files/md_goz_final_en_r4_4.pdf https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/strategies/polands-circular-economy-roadmap
RO	The National Strategy regarding the Circular Economy https://dezvoltaredurabila.gov.ro/strategia-nationala-privind-economia-circulara-13409762 ORDINANCE no. 6 of August 25, 2021 regarding the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment https://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocument/245908
RS	Circular Economy Development Programme in the Republic of Serbia for the period 2022 to 2024, https://www.cirkularnezajednice.rs/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Program-for-development-of-circular-economy-in-the-Republic-of-Serbia-for-the-period-2022-2024.pdf Waste management program of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2022-2031 https://www.ekologija.gov.rs/sites/default/files/2022-03/program_upravljanja_otpadom_eng_-_adopted_version.pdf
SI	Roadmap towards the Circular Economy in Slovenia Framework Programme for the Transition to a Green Economy
SK	Greener Slovakia – The Strategy of the Environmental Policy of the Slovak Republic until 2030 Circular Economy Roadmap https://www.minzp.sk/obehove-hospodarstvo/cestovna-mapa/

Table 12: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Energy and Climate

Country	Energy and Climate
BG	<p>Integrated plan for energy and climate of the Republic of Bulgaria 2021 – 2030.</p> <p>Climate Change Limitation Act, 2014</p> <p>Long-term climate change mitigation strategy until 2050 of the Republic of Bulgaria</p> <p>National Climate Change Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan to 2030.</p>
CZ	<p>Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan</p> <p>National plan of the Czech Republic in the field of energy and climate https://www.dataplan.info/img_upload/7bdb1584e3b8a53d337518d988763f8d/vnitrostani-plan-cr-v-oblasti-energetiky-a-klimatu_final.pdf</p> <p>Climate protection policy in Czech republic https://www.dataplan.info/img_upload/7bdb1584e3b8a53d337518d988763f8d/pok.pdf</p> <p>UPDATE OF THE NATIONAL PROGRAM REDUCTION OF EMISSIONS OF THE CZECH REPUBLIC https://www.dataplan.info/img_upload/7bdb1584e3b8a53d337518d988763f8d/ooo-aktualizace_npse_2019-final-20200217.pdf</p>
GR	<p>Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan</p> <p>National Climate Change Adaptation Strategy (NCCAS)</p>
HU	<p>Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan</p> <p>National Climate Change Strategy 2</p> <p>National Energy Strategy 2030</p>
HR	<p>Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan</p>
PL	<p>Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan https://www.gov.pl/web/klimat/national-energy-and-climate-plan-for-the-years-2021-2030</p> <p>A strategy for district heating up to 2030 with an outlook to 2040, https://bip.mos.gov.pl/strategie-plany-programy/strategia-dla-cieplownictwa-do-2030-r-z-perspektywa-do-2040-r/</p> <p>National Program for Air Protection https://bip.mos.gov.pl/strategie-plany-programy/krajowy-program-ochrony-powietrza/</p> <p>National Program for Reducing Air Pollution https://bip.mos.gov.pl/strategie-plany-programy/krajowy-program-ograniczania-zanieczyszczenia-powietrza/</p> <p>Energy Policy of Poland until 2040 https://bip.mos.gov.pl/fileadmin/user_upload/bip/strategie_plany_programy/Polityka_energetyczna_Polski/Strzeszenie_PEP2040_EN_2021-01-27.pdf</p> <p>Polish Hydrogen Strategy until 2030 with a perspective until 2040 https://bip.mos.gov.pl/strategie-plany-programy/polska-strategia-wodorowa-do-roku-2030-z-perspektywa-do-2040-r/</p>
RO	<p>Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-06/ro_final_necp_main_en_0.pdf</p> <p>ROMANIA'S LONG-TERM STRATEGY FOR REDUCING GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS http://www.mmediu.ro/app/webroot/uploads/files/Strategia%20%20pe%20Termen%20Lung%20a%20RO%20pentru%20Reducerea%20Emisiilor%20de%20GES.pdf</p>
RS	<p>Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan of the Republic of Serbia until 2030.</p> <p>https://www.mre.gov.rs/en/dokumenta/ostalo/integrated-national-energy-and-climate-plan-republic-serbia-until-2030</p>

SI	Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan
SK	<p>Integrated National Energy and Climate plan of the Slovak Republic for 2021 - 2030 https://www.mhsr.sk/uploads/files/zsrwR58V.pdf</p> <p>Strategy of climate change adaptation of the Slovak Republic https://www.minzp.sk/files/odbor-politiky-zmeny-klimy/strategia-adaptacie-sr-zmenu-klimy-aktualizacia.pdf</p> <p>Low-carbon strategy of the Slovak Republic until 2030 with a view to 2050 https://www.minzp.sk/klima/nizkohlukova-strategia/</p> <p>Low-carbon development strategy of the Slovak Republic until 2030 with a view to 2050</p> <p>National Hydrogen Strategy: Ready for the future https://www.mhsr.sk/uploads/files/YBN0ndkU.pdf?csrc=1658888424339760523</p>

Table 13: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Renewable Energy

Country	Renewable Energy
BG	Renewable Energy Act, 2011
CZ	
GR	
HU	<p>National Renewable Energy Action Plan (2010-2020) https://www.mmk.hu/dokumentumok/20200117_nemzetienergiastrategia2030</p>
HR	
PL	<p>Act of 27 January 2022 amending the Act on renewable energy sources and the Act amending the Act on renewable energy sources and certain other acts https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20220000467</p>
RO	
RS	<p>National action plan for use of renewable energy sources Republic of Serbia https://arhiva.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/02%20Nacionalni%20akcioni%20plan%20za%20koriscenje%20obnovljivih%20izvora%20energije%20u%20Republici%20Srbiji1.pdf</p> <p>Law on the use of renewable energy sources, https://www.mre.gov.rs/sites/default/files/2021/06/res_law.pdf</p>
SI	
SK	<p>Strategy for higher use of Renewable Energy Sources in Slovakia https://www.enviroportal.sk/energetika/strategia-vysieho-vyuzitia-obnovitelnych-zdrojov-energie-v-sr</p>

Table 14: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Farm to Fork Strategy

Country	Farm to Fork Strategy
BG	<p>Draft Action Plan to Farm to Fork draft Strategy, 2020</p> <p>The National Science Program "Healthy Foods for a Strong Bioeconomy and Quality of Life", 2020.</p>
CZ	
GR	
HU	<p>Medium and long-term food industry development strategy 2014-2020</p> <p>Food Industry Concept of Hungary 2017-2050</p>

HR	
PL	Poland has signed up to the EU's 'Farm to fork' strategy and is aligning individual pieces of legislation with the strategy's provisions. Some of the elements are included in the Common Agricultural Policy
RO	
RS	
SI	
SK	

Table 15: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Industry Strategy

Country	Industry Strategy
BG	National strategy for small and medium-sized enterprises in Bulgaria 2021-2027.
CZ	National Recovery Plan - Plan for the revival and resilience of the Czech Republic https://www.dataplan.info/img_upload/7bdb1584e3b8a53d337518d988763f8d/konsolidovane-zneni-narodniho-planu-obnovy_2021-09-08.pdf
GR	National Strategy for the Industry and Action Plan
HU	
HR	
PL	Poland's position on the EU industrial policy strategy to 2030 https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&ved=2ahUKEwjvz5_CiNz-AhWPxosKHUdCBL4QFnoECBUQAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.gov.pl%2Fattachment%2F92d546be-2289-459d-b2d8-8d88a2c8e5db&usq=AOvVaw3Al23J-1C_cd7x1hJhTz8T Polish Industrial Policy https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwjig_2siNz-AhUGI4sKHxpsAw0QFnoECAoQAQ&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.gov.pl%2Fattachment%2F555c07a8-4d95-49af-9ec1-282fafdbcac5&usq=AOvVaw1n80rSkzPhEPBuyvJ0LF7 " https://www.gov.pl/web/rozwoj-technologie/strategia-produktywnosci-2031
RO	Rumanian Industrial Policy https://oldeconomie.gov.ro/images/politici-industriale/SIPOCA7/Document%20de%20Politica%20Industrial%20a%20Romaniei.pdf
RS	Industrial Policy Strategy of the Republic of Serbia from 2021 to 2030 https://privreda.gov.rs/sites/default/files/documents/2021-08/Industrial-Policy-Strategy-2021-2030.pdf Smart Specialisation Strategy of the Republic of Serbia 2020 – 2027 https://pametnaspecijalizacija.mpn.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/Strategija-pametne-specijalizacije_EN_WEB.pdf
SI	Slovenian Industrial Strategy https://www.gzs.si/Portals/206/Slovenska%20industrijska%20strategija.pdf
SK	Economic Policy Strategy until 2030 https://www.economy.gov.sk/uploads/files/wRKb2ncO.pdf

Table 16: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries - Environment

Country	Environment
BG	
CZ	State Environmental Policy of Czech Republic 2030 https://www.mzp.cz/C1257458002F0DC7/cz/statni_politika_zivotniho_prostredi/\$FILE/OPZPUR-statni_politika_zp_2030_s_vyhledem_2050-20220615.pdf

GR	
HU	Fifth National Environmental Programme 2021-2026 National Clean Development Strategy 2020-2050 National Environmental Technology Innovation Strategy 2011-2020
HR	
PL	National ecological policy 2030 - development strategy in the field of environment and water management https://bip.mos.gov.pl/strategie-plany-programy/polityka-ekologiczna-panstwa/polityka-ekologiczna-panstwa-2030-strategia-rozwoju-w-obszarze-srodowiska-i-gospodarki-wodnej/ The 2030 Environmental Policy https://bip.mos.gov.pl/fileadmin/user_upload/bip/strategie_plany_programy/Polityka_Ekologiczna_Panstwa/Polityka%20Ekologiczna%20Pa%C5%84stwa%202030%20ENG_wersja%20internet.pdf
RO	
RS	National Environmental approximation Strategy for the Republic of Serbia http://www.misp-serbia.rs/wp-content/uploads/2010/05/EAS-Strategija-ENG-FINAL.pdf
SI	
SK	

Table 17: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – National Development

Country	National Development
BG	
CZ	Strategic Framework Czech Republic 2030
GR	
HU	National Development 2030 - National Development and Territorial Development Concept
HR	
PL	National Regional Development Strategy https://www.gov.pl/web/fundusze-regiony/krajowa-strategia-rozwoju-regionalnego
RO	Romanian RDI Strategy for 2014-2020 Romanian Strategy for Competitiveness 2014-2020
RS	Serbia and 2030 Agenda Mapping the National Strategic Framework vis-a-vis the Sustainable Development Goals https://rsjp.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/Serbia-and-2030-Agenda_November-2021.pdf
SI	Slovenian Development Strategy 2030
SK	

Table 18: Titles and references to implemented strategies in CEE2ACT target countries – Rural Development

Country	Rural Development
BG	Strategic plan for the development of agriculture and rural areas 2023-2027. OPINION on "Viable and sustainable rural areas in Bulgaria in the context of the long-term vision of the EU", 2023.
CZ	

	https://www.dataplan.info/img_upload/7bdb1584e3b8a53d337518d988763f8d/pur_cr_ve-zneni-zavaznem-od-1_9_2021_brozura_en_final.pdf
GR	The Rural Development Programme (2014-2020)
HU	New Hungary Rural Development Programme 2014-2020 https://kormany.hu/dokumentumtar/magyarorszag-kap-strategiai-terve-2023-2027
HR	
PL	The Strategy for Sustainable Development of Rural Areas, Agriculture and Fisheries 2014-2020 (national sectoral strategy - in updating process) Plan for Rural Areas (bioeconomy as one of the priority projects named Agriculture for Ecology) https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo/dokumenty-analizy-szrwir-2030
RO	
RS	Strategy of agriculture and rural development of the Republic Serbia for the period 2014-2024 https://uap.gov.rs/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/STRATEGIJA-2014-2020-.pdf
SI	
SK	

3.2 Bioeconomy related infrastructure

Country's hard facts

Every country has different settings and economics which influences directly and indirectly the progress of bioeconomy implementation. Figure 3 shows the GDP per capita normalized to NL, which has the highest GDP with EUR 47,000 per capita.

Figure 3: Gross Domestic Product per Capita (normalized to NL) (data retrieved from Worldbank; data from 2019)

Turnover of bioeconomy related sectors

An economy based on renewable raw materials is a key component for a successful bioeconomy implementation. To explore the current status of the market in each country, the turnover was extracted in Figure 4 as this indicator is available for different bioeconomy sectors (contrary to the indicator “value added” that would be though more representative but is not disaggregated for bioeconomy sectors).

“The turnover is used as a market size indicator in the EU bioeconomy strategy. The turnover of a given sector represents the value of sales from this sector. The turnover of the whole bioeconomy includes all the sales from the different activity sectors that compose the bioeconomy, including the sales of products from one sector to a downstream sector of the bioeconomy. It thus leads to occasional double counting throughout the value chain.” (EU dashboard)

Figure 4 shows the contribution of each sector that is related to bioeconomy by turnover. The largest sector is ‘Food, Beverage, Tobacco’ with an average contribution of 41% across all CEE2ACT countries including the Baltic States, followed by ‘Agriculture’ with 21% on average and ‘Wood, wood products & furniture’ with 13% on average. One can see differences especially in relation to wood, wood products and furniture where the Baltic States have a much higher share than the other countries. On the other hand, agriculture has a higher share in most of the CEE2ACT target countries than in the contributing countries and the Baltic States. Forestry stands out in the forest-rich countries FI, SE, EE and LV. In FI and SE as well as in AT, pulp and paper is above average. Biobased chemicals play a larger role in AT, BE, DE, but also SI and HU.

Figure 4: Contribution of sectors related to bioeconomy by turnover (data retrieved from European Commission 2023a; data from 2019)

Biomass production and consumption

A prerequisite of a bio-based industry is a stable and sustainable supply of biomass. The biomass can be produced in the agricultural and forestry sector or in fisheries (incl. aquaculture). The most biomass is produced in agriculture, followed by forestry (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Biomass production in CEE2ACT countries incl. Baltic States (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b; data from 2016/2017)

Especially in the forest-rich countries currently already a lot of renewable energy produced from biomass. Similarly, the use of materials for biomass is well above average in AT, FI, SE and EE.

Figure 6 shows the total biomass that is consumed for energy (in blue) and for materials (in orange). It can be noticed that the biomass consumption for energy is dominating in most countries except NL, GR and PL. and that the amount per capita is largely different between countries.

Figure 6: Total Biomass consumed (kg dry matter/capita) (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b; data from 2017)

In relation to the number of inhabitants, the forest-rich countries FI and AT as well as the Baltic states are again those that show the highest values for the consumption of biomass

Energy sector

The energy sector is of high relevance to the bioeconomy as it is the most relevant sector in the use of fossil fuels. According to the EGD the net greenhouse gas emissions shall be zero by 2050. A transformation to a fossil-free energy sector is therefore of the utmost importance.

The origin of renewable energy is country specific. With more than 50% as mean value primary solid fuel is the most represented having a share of more than 75% in all Baltic countries. Beside AT and SE also in HR, RO, RS and SI the share of hydro power is above 20 %. What is striking is the good distribution of different renewable sources in Greece

using beside hydropower and solid biomass also solar thermal and solar photovoltaic energy, wind energy and heat pumps in a share of about or more than 10%. Overall the use of solar and wind energy in target countries certainly can be expanded. Shares above 10% are only recorded for PL and RO, whereas the mean value in contributing countries is above 15 %. Outstanding is the use of geothermal energy in HU, which is with more than 5 % showing the highest value of all countries. Also, pure bio-gasoline is used in HU much more than in all other countries. The use of renewable municipal solid waste for heat production in general in target countries is showing a huge potential comparing the mean value from contributing countries (5.6 %) with the low stake of 0.8 % in target countries. Only BG is using municipal solid waste with more than 2 % for their renewable energy production.

Figure 7: Renewable Energy Production Mix (data from EUROSTAT)

The current status of the energy sector is necessary to detect potentials and to foster the expansion of renewable energy. For this reason, the share of renewable energy in each country was considered as well as the share of renewables for transport, electricity, heating & cooling.

Figure 8: Share of renewables for transport (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b; data from 2017)

The share of renewables for transport is generally low with an average value of 7% (Figure 8). This is due to the still high importance of vehicles with combustion engines and the low technical applicability of renewables in the fuel. Potential to increase this share is rated as low due to the electrification of the transport sector and the use of synthetic fuels in this sector. The share of renewables for transport will largely depend on technological feasibility and further developments of fuels and engines.

If we look at the three groups of countries separately, we see that the average share of renewable transport in the target countries is twice as high as in the Baltic States, and that the share of renewable transport in the contributing counties is twice as high as in the target countries. However, the range of variation is large. The comparatively low shares in HR and SI are striking.

The picture changes if we look at the share of renewable energies used for electricity generation. Besides Austria and Sweden, HR, RO and LV stand out with values above 50%. The share of renewables for electricity over all countries is on average 31% across all CEE2ACT countries including Baltic States with the lowest share in the Hungary (8%). It can be seen in Figure 8 that there is still high potential to increase the share in many countries.

The share of renewables for heating and cooling is on average 30% across all CEE2ACT countries including Baltic States with the highest share in Sweden (66%) and the lowest in the Netherlands (6%). It can be seen in Figure 10 that there is still high potential to increase the share in many countries.

Figure 9: Share of renewables for electricity (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b; data from 2017)

Figure 10: Share of renewables for heating & cooling (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b ; data from 2017)

Waste sector

An economy based on circularity is a major component of a successful bioeconomy implementation. For this, a well-established waste management sector is advantageous with the focus of material recycling to keep the material in the loop (as aimed for in the Circular Economy Action Plan). Organic residues and waste are another source of biomass. Examples are, e.g. using organic residues of processing industry to produce other products (valorisation), recycling of organic residues into compost (composting), recycling of untreated wooden products to produce other products (material recycling, or downcycling).

Biomass refers to any organic material that can be used as a renewable energy source. Biowaste, such as food scraps, agricultural residues, and animal manure, contains organic compounds that can be converted into bioenergy through various processes like anaerobic digestion, composting or combustion. These methods harness the energy stored in the organic matter and can be used for heat generation, electricity production, or biofuel generation. By utilizing bio waste as part of biomass, we can reduce waste, promote sustainable practices, and contribute to renewable energy production. When we use biowaste as compost, we can return the nutrients we have removed from the soil and rebuild the important humus layer.

Figure 11: Comparison of generated and recovered biowaste from households (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b; data from 2018)

Biowaste as shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12 based on the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System dashboards (European Commission, 2023b) include animal faeces, urine and manure, vegetal waste, animal and mixed food waste, textile waste, wood waste, rubber waste, paper and cardboard waste.

In average the amount of biowaste generated by households in contributing countries is much higher (153 kg/capita) than in target countries (63 kg/capita) and also higher as in the Baltic States (85 kg/capita). The recovery rate in contributing countries (135 kg/capita) is accordingly also higher than in target countries (25 kg/capita) and in the Baltic States (48 kg/capita). Figure 10 shows the great potential of waste management in all target countries, but also in individual contributing countries (ES), where the current recovery rates are below 50 %, with a few exceptions.

Figure 12: Comparison of generated and recovered biowaste in total (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b; data from 2018)

The generated and recovered biowaste in total (biowaste from households and from Industry and Agriculture) give a similar picture with some countries showing outstanding collection volumes, like Belgium, Finland and the Netherlands. In general, the amount of biowaste generated in target countries is lower than in contributing countries showing also lower recovery rates.

Recycling of biowaste

Focusing on biowaste in the narrow sense according to Directive (EU) 2018/851 this comprises biodegradable garden and park waste, food and kitchen waste from households, offices, restaurants, wholesale, canteens, caterers and retail premises and comparable waste from food processing plants one can see that targeting countries are far below contributing countries comparing the recycling in kg of biowaste per capita based on the Guidance for separate collection of municipal waste (Dubois et al. 2020)

Figure 13: Recycling of bio-waste in Europe in 2017 (Kg bio-waste per capita) Dubois et al. (2020)

Figure 3.2 Bio-waste collected separately as a share of bio-waste generated (bio-waste capture rate), by country for 32 EEA member and cooperating countries, 2017

Figure 14: Separate collection of biowaste

Figure 14 shows that the separate collection rate of biowaste in target countries is, with the exception of CZ and SI below the European average. Especially in GR, HR and RO the collection rate is below 20 %. Here can be seen a huge potential for the future. According to EEA 2020 sufficient treatment capacity for all municipal bio-waste generated is available in AT, NL, SE but also in SI from target countries. These countries' treatment capacity exceeds the volume of municipal bio-waste generated.

Treatment capacity is available for the separately collected municipal bio-waste but not for all of the municipal bio-waste generated in BE and ES from contributing countries in LV and in four of CEE2ACT target countries (HU, PL, RO, SK): These countries are

currently able to treat all of the separately collected municipal bio-waste, given their installed treatment capacity. However, as separate collection increases, the installed treatment infrastructure will need to be extended. HR according to EEA (2020) has plenty of anaerobic treatment capacity, but most plants only process animal by-products, and their spatial distribution does not necessarily match the location of bio-waste generation. Insufficient treatment capacity for the separately collected municipal bio-waste was detected for ES and GR. These countries are currently not able to (theoretically) treat the volume of bio-waste generated, nor are they able to treat all separately collected bio-waste. Extended use of bio-waste will therefore require the installation of new treatment capacity. No information was available for other countries.

3.3 Bioeconomy ecosystem conditions

Agricultural and forestry areas

In order to be able to use biomass in accordance with the bioeconomy idea, the corresponding potential must be available in the countries. It can be seen that there are in part large differences in the theoretically usable potential of biomass in the countries. FI and SE (7.4 % and 7.5 %) have by far the lowest shares of arable land in relation to the total area. SE, NL, HU and RO, on the other hand, each have over 50%. The opposite is true for the forest area, which is very low in NL with less than 11%, but BE, GR, PL and RO also have low forest areas with less than or just over 30%.

Figure 15: Share of arable land and forest area in CEE2ACT countries (data retrieved from Worldbank, data from 2019)

If one considers the arable land and the existing forest area in relation to the inhabitants, the large potential of forest in FI (40.6 km²/1000EW), SE (27.4 km²/1000EW) as well as

EE and LV (about 18 km²/1000 inh.) becomes even clearer. At the other side in NL, DE and BE the value is below 1.5 km²/1000 inh. Biggest potential on arable land compared to the number of inhabitants can be seen in the Baltic Countries but also FI, BG, HU and RO have more than 0.4 km² of arable land per inhabitant. Below 0.1 km²/inh could be shown for BE, NL as well as SI.

The share of organic farming is also different in CEE2ACT countries (Figure 19). In AT, SE and EE the share of organic farming is above 20%. In NL, BG, PL and RO at the moment the contribution on organic farming is below 5%.

Figure 16: Share of organic farming in CEE2ACT countries (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b; data from 2019)

Environmental health

Natural resources need to be managed sustainably. The following indicators can be used to interpret the status of environmental health in each country.

- Biochemical oxygen demand in rivers: Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) is used to measure water quality. The cleanest rivers have BOD₅ values of less than 1 mg O₂/L, moderately and heavily polluted rivers show values ranging from 2 to 8 mg O₂/L.

- Phosphate in rivers: Refers to concentration of phosphate (PO₄) in the dissolved phase of water samples. At high levels, phosphate can cause water quality problems, such as eutrophication, by triggering the growth of macrophytes and algae.
- Nitrate in groundwater: Indicator refers to concentrations of nitrate (NO₃) in groundwater. According to the Drinking Water Directive, a maximum concentration of 50 mg/L of nitrate in groundwater that is used for drinking water is allowed.

		BOD in rivers (mg O ₂ /l)	Phosphate in rivers (mg PO ₄ /l)	Nitrate in ground-water (mgNO ₃ / l)
Contributing countries	AT	1,68	0,03	21,92
	BE	2,68	0,2	30,6
	DE	n.a	0,06	27,55
	ES	n.a	n.a	n.a
	FI	n.a	0,01	n.a
	NL	n.a	n.a	n.a
	SE	n.a	0,01	n.a
Targeted Countries	BG	2,28	0,1	29,79
	CZ	2,61	0,14	17,98
	GR	n.a	n.a	n.a
	HR	1,85	0,03	n.a
	HU	n.a	n.a	n.a
	PL	2,95	n.a	n.a
	RO	3,48	0,08	n.a
	RS	n.a	n.a	n.a
	SI	0,86	0,02	18,25
	SK	2,17	0,07	14,38
Baltic States	EE	1,54	0,03	5,1
	LT	2,35	0,12	n.a
	LV	1,26	0,06	n.a
Maximum concentration				50
n.a. ... not available				

Figure 17: Water contamination in CEE2ACT countries (data retrieved from European Commission, 2023b; data from 2019) (colours indicate values that are beyond (red) and within (green) certain thresholds per indicator with different shades in between)

Not from all countries are data available but Figure 17 shows that there are still countries that have elevated pollution levels in water bodies. Figure 14 shows for BOD even more clearly that there is a need for action in a number of countries. Especially in RO, PL, CZ and ES where more than 25% of rivers are affected.

Figure 18: water pollution (BOD in rivers) in CEE2ACT countries (data retrieved from European Environment Agency, 2020; data from 2016-2018)

Similarly, as across entire Europe, in some CEE regions an increase in the area of arable land not connected with animal production is observed. These areas are characterised by a lack of manure, a classical source of organic matter for soil in agriculture. There is a strong spatial differentiation in the type of agricultural production. Animal production is concentrated in some regions, which may put pressure on the water environment from excess of nutrients. On the other hand, in other regions there is a significant deficit of organic fertilizers, resulting from the abandonment of animal production. Figure 19 presents a regional diversity of livestock density is observed also across selected BIOEAST countries (Dach et al, 2022).

Figure 19: Regional diversity of livestock density across BIOEAST countries (Dach et al., 2022, based on EUROSTAT)

Soil organic matter (SOM) content varies across Europe. A loss of SOM is forecasted for around 30% of the European area under current land management practices, especially in the Southern part of Europe. Soil can be a source of or a sink for carbon depending on its management. SOC levels in BIOEAST countries are diversified. However, except Estonia and Slovenia, most countries rather suffer low SOC levels, at least in some regions (Figure 20). The lowest SOC is observed in Poland, mostly since the soil cover is dominated by light soil texture. Low content of clay fraction limits accumulation of humus in soils. Therefore, the role of exogenous organic matter is critical for maintaining the level of organic matter in the soil. Organic fertilisers applied to soil can be a significant source of soil carbon. It must be emphasized that only safe (uncontaminated) organic materials can be applied to soil. Organic soil amendments might include animal manure or recycled organic matter, e.g. compost, composted sludge, food waste, digestate (Dach et al., 2022).

Figure 20: Soil organic carbon (SOC) in soils of BIOAST countries (Dach et al., 2022, based on LUCAS soil monitoring database)

3.4 Bioeconomy initiatives

In total 77 collaboration initiatives were collected from target countries, each using different names for their initiatives such as association, centre, club, cluster, cooperation, forum, hub, initiative, network platform, round table, seminar and workshop (see Table 19). A full list of initiatives and contacts is shown in Annex 7.3.

Table 19: Number and type of initiatives per target country

Type	BG	CZ	EL	HU	PL	RO	RS	SI	SK	HR	Total
Association		1			1	2			3		7
Centre			2				1	1	1		5
Club						1					1
Cluster				1	7	6	1		4		19
Cooperation					1			1			2
Forum			1								1
Hub						1		1			2
Initiative					1	1					2
Other	3						3	6	1		13
Platform		1			3						4
R&D	5			1				1			7
Round table	1										1
Seminar	2										2
Workshop	3										3
Other			1	1		6					8
Total per country	14	2	4	3	13	17	5	10	9		77

Experts from target countries were asked to attribute the initiatives to specific sectors (multiple choices were possible). Table 20 shows an overview. Most of the initiatives were attributed to the agricultural sector (32 initiatives), followed by the food sector (23), organic waste (19), bioenergy (17) and forestry (12). Also, other sectors were named such as bio-based pharmaceuticals, bio-based plastics or other fields of elaboration such as environmental protection, circular economy, eco-construction, rural development. The least initiatives are present in sector pulp and paper (6) and bio-based textiles (4).

Table 20: Number of initiatives and their attributed sectors per target country (multiple choices for sectors per initiative possible)

Sectors	BG	CZ	EL	HU	PL	RO	RS	SI	SK	Total number
Agriculture	6	2	1	1	9	5	2	2	4	32
Forestry	4	2	1		3	1	1			12
Fisheries		2			5					7
Aquaculture		2			6					8
Organic waste	3	2	1	1	8		1	2	1	19
Food	6	1	1		7	2	1	2	3	23
Wood, wood products & furniture	3	1	1	1	3	1	1		1	12
Pulp & paper		1	1		3		1			6
Biotechnology	1	1		1	9		1			13
Bio-based textiles			1		3					4
Bio-base chemicals and materials	3			1	6			2	1	13
Bioenergy (incl. Transport biofuels)	3	1	1	1	6	1		1	3	17
Ecosystem services		1	2		3				2	8
Other specific sectors:		1			10	3			3	17

Other collaborations contributing to the development of bioeconomy in the CEE target countries encompass cooperation with ministries, participation in meetings, conferences etc. The following list is exemplary and represents only a small part of the actual activities.

- Meeting at Agricultural University Plovdiv regional hub for bioeconomy – Plovdiv (BG)
- Mission Green Bulgaria (BG)
- Annual working meeting of the National Scientific Program "Healthy Foods for a Strong Bioeconomy and Quality of Life" (NNP-FOOD) at the Ministry of Education and Science (BG)
- Regional agency for the development of small and medium size enterprises Alma Mons d.o.o., Novi Sad (RS)
- Ministry of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia - Group for the circular and green economy (RS)
- Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Serbia (RS)
- Slovak Agriculture and Food Chamber (SK)
- Circular bioeconomy strategy (SI)

- Strategic Research and Innovation Partnership Circular economy (SI)
- Deep Demonstration in Slovenia (SI)
- Value Chain Generator (SI)
- WoodChainManager (SI)
- TBMCE 2023 6th International Conference Technologies and Business Models for Circular Economy (SI)
- Roadmap towards circular economy in Slovenia (SI)
- Whey2Value technology to convert acid waste whey (SI)
- Cooperation agreement for the development of the biogas and biomethane sector (PL)
- The 'Bioeconomy Development Group' initiative (PL)

Also, RDI (Research, Development and Innovation) related initiatives were mentioned by some experts, but not by all. That is why they are not included in the tables above. Such RDI are for example:

- Presentation "BIOECONOMY: THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY OF THE FUTURE" (BG)
- Study of the potential of the bioeconomy in Bulgaria (BG)
- AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY - PLOVDIV PRESENTED SUCCESSFUL EUROPEAN EXAMPLES IN THE BIOECONOMY (BG)
- A successful example in the field of bioeconomy (BG)
- Analysis and profile of the state and potential of a regional bioeconomy (BG)
- Institute for Bio-Economy and Agri-Technology (iBO) (GR)
- BIOEAST (HU)
- BIORURAL Romania (RO)
- Alps4GreenC - Biochar potential in the region (SI)
- New Strategies on Bio-economy in Poland (BioeCon) (PL)

4. Challenges and potentials of bioeconomy implementation

4.1 Challenges reported from experts from target countries

Around 58 entries for challenges were mentioned by experts from target countries. The challenges are grouped into specific categories related to specific topics of bioeconomy. Table 21 gives an overview of the topics mentioned per country. Please note that this table shall only give an orientation of the topics of the potentials, but is not complete. For further details, it is referred to the Annex 7.4.

Table 21: Topics related to challenges of bioeconomy implementation reported from experts

Country / Category	BG	CZ	GR	HU	PL	RO	SI	SK	SR
Financial barriers	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Knowledge barriers					x	x	x		x
Lack of awareness				x	x	x		x	x
Lack of collaboration	x		x	x	x			x	
Lack of implementation								x	
Lack of infrastructure and capacities	x			x	x	x			x
Lack of market demand					x				
Lack of motivation		x		x	x		x		
Lack of policy				x	x	x	x	x	
Legal barriers		x	x		x		x	x	x

Experts from targeting countries faced several challenges for bioeconomy in their countries. All recognized challenges in the area of “Financial barriers”, very often connected with “missing legal /policy aspects” and a “lack of collaboration” among the respective actors, often due to “missing knowledge/awareness” in this area.

Most significant challenges for implementing a bioeconomy with regard to **Financial barriers** is the lack of funding and investment, which is crucial for building the needed infrastructure and supporting research and development. Most see the responsibilities for funding at the state level. Funding is important not only for research and development, but especially for companies, as there are high initial investments required to implement the Bioeconomy principles. Also the private sector should be engaged in financially supporting bioeconomy actions.

The existing regulatory and **legal frameworks** in different countries (CZ, GR, PL, SI, SK, SI) are not supportive for establishing bioeconomy and can be seen as a barrier to the growth and development of the sector. In some countries, bioeconomy initiatives and projects already exist, but at the legal level, the bioeconomy does not appear at all. This is seen as a **lack of policy** as bioeconomy is an essential part of transition to sustainability in HU, PL, RO, SI, SK. There is a need to support the bioeconomy through the

development and implementation of policies, action plans, innovative business models, and financing systems to enable development.

Not only government or companies but also in public there is still a big **lack of awareness** (HU, PL, RO, SK, SR) or interest in bioeconomy often connected with **missing knowledge** (PL, RO, SI, SR) of the topic. Awareness is dealing in a more general way with the content, potentials and challenges in bioeconomy context. Lacks of knowledge are existing companies regarding circularity, accelerating bioeconomy and sustainability or on a scientific point of view. Also it is not known, that there are already existing structures in the field of bioeconomy, but that the development on a higher and comprehensive level need more support, starting with knowledge transfer to related actors.

The obstacles mentioned so far also do not help to **motivate** the public and especially companies to implement activities to support bioeconomy. A need to introduce bioeconomy strategy tools that would lead to motivation within the bioeconomy was recognised in four of the countries.

Lack of knowledge and of motivation leads also, but not only, to **missing collaboration** recognised in BG, GR, HU, PL and SK. As bioeconomy is an inclusive strategy, stakeholders and actors from national to local level, inter- and transdisciplinary have to be included to force a strong, sustainable bioeconomy in the country.

Some specific challenges were additionally mentioned by BG, HU, PL, RO and SR in terms of missing **infrastructure and capacities**. A lack of procedures and structures enabling a redesign of technological processes to prevent the consumption of unnecessary resources, professional personnel in the field of Bioeconomy was determined.

In SK a lack of implementation of already existing strategies was recognised; and for PL additionally the creation of a specific market demand for bio-based products would have seen as necessary to establish a functioning and sustainable bioeconomy system.

4.2 Challenges reported in BIOEAST concept papers

Around 71 entries for challenges were extracted from BIOEAST concept papers. The challenges are grouped into specific categories related to specific topics of bioeconomy. Table 22 gives an overview of the topics mentioned per country. Please note that this table shall only give an orientation of the topics of the potentials, but is not complete. For further details, it is referred to the Annex 7.4.

Most challenges for bioeconomy in the target countries (out of BIOEAST concept papers) are cited in the sector of “agriculture” with strong connections to “forestry” and “Biomass use” followed by challenges in the sector of “governance and policy” and in the “Research, Development and Innovation (RDI)” sector.

All targeting countries facing challenges within the **Agriculture** sector. Challenges are dealing with ensuring biodiversity and functioning of ecosystems, and adaptation to climate change in general. More concrete challenges are the increasing or decreasing and partly unknown and unused biomass flows (BG, HR, CZ, HU, RO), sustainable crop breeding as well as organic farming (CZ, PL, RO) and on the other hand efficient land use (LV, PL, SI, EE).

Within the **Forestry** sector, damage to forest areas are additional strains as well as efficient use of biomass (SI, HU, LV). Streaming bioenergy towards **Decarbonisation** presents some countries (CZ, SK, SI) with many challenges. The mentioned countries have a lot of forest-related territories. The use of biomass can reduce gas emission and contribute to the country's decarbonisation.

The increase of the efficiency of **biomass use** and waste stream recycling is an important aspect on the pathway to a growing bioeconomy in HR, EE, PL, LT and RO. Challenges are faced with regard to waste and by-products of biological origin (LT, EE, HR). In terms of **Bioenergy** the lack of a strong biogas and bio methane sector is another burden recognized in Poland.

Table 22: Topics related to challenges of bioeconomy implementation reported in BIOEAST concept papers

Country/ Category	BG	CZ	EE	HR	HU	LT	LV	PL	RO	SI	SK
Agriculture	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x
Forestry					x		x	x		x	
Balance /nature						x		x	x		
Biochemical industry	x										
Bioenergy								x			
Biomass use			x	x		x		x	x		
Biorefineries					x				x		
Capacity building					x	x		x			
Collaboration						x				x	x
Decarbonisation		x								x	x
Fisheries & aquaculture			x				x	x			
Food	x			x	x						
Freshwater					x				x		
Governance & policy	x		x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x
RDI			x	x			x			x	
Resources / technology		x				x		x			
Wood & wood products	x		x				x				

Changes in the system of **Governance and Policy** are paramount factor affecting the bioeconomy development and implementation. When developing, often challenges in

terms of unclear roles and guidelines, low connectivity and political willingness are faced. Nevertheless, within the countries (SK, BG, HR, EE, LV, RO, PL, HU, SI) and the different sectors only in the interaction and **collaboration** (in an inter- and transdisciplinary way) and exchange of science and technology, politics, economy and society is it possible to develop a functioning bioeconomy.

Challenges in terms of **RDI** were reported in terms of low financing and tax incentives as well as uncertain business environment (HR, EE, LV, SI) when it comes to supporting innovation development. A lack of missing cooperation between different actors, as already pointed out in previous sector, are additional burdens recognized in different countries (EE, HR, SI).

It is also described in the **Capacity building** assignment, that challenges in terms of bioeconomy are missing knowledge transfer with national and transnational actors (PL, HU) but also lacking labour skills. The lack of jobs in the high-value levels of Bioeconomy on the one hand, and the loss of workforce and manpower to other countries on the other hand are challenges with which LT and PL are struggling.

In terms of the **Food** sector, challenges exist along the entire food value chain starting with insufficient raw material (base) and technologies, qualified labour, high requirements for quality and safety to low awareness to the food waste problem and prevention resp. use of food waste (HR, BG, HU).

With regard to the **Fishery and Aquaculture** sector the main challenge is to improve the use of the existing fish resources and to develop cultivation technologies and find a market for algae and shells (EE). In LV the fishing for cod was prohibited due to the degradation. In PL the greatest challenge is the development of the inland aquaculture that requires financial support, sustainable business model including cooperation among different actors.

Challenges in **Wood Industry** are the changes towards innovative products e.g. textiles from wood or thermal packaging (LV) or the usage of nanomaterials in furniture industry (BG) that requires intensified RDI activities, financing possibilities and improved cooperation among all stakeholders.

Improvement of the **Biochemical industry** in general was named as challenge for BG. With regard to **Biorefineries** HU has faced several challenges in securing fuel supply while RO is struggling with adapted sizes of refineries in the country. Just before establishing biorefineries, the pathways for transformation of the sector of chemicals and chemical products need to be efficiently tackled before the potentials of this transformation pathway is exploited. The first challenge is inter-sectoral cooperation among bioeconomy sectors, which is rather low, resulting in broken, incomplete value chains in PL and RO.

In these two countries, but also valid for all other countries (like LT), a key challenge is to find a **balance** between circular economy efforts including sustainability aspects with regard to nature and climate and economic development. The lack of **resources and technology** in Bioeconomy and the circular and sustainable valorisation of the available bio resources in several fields leads to challenges in PL, LT and CZ.

Challenges in terms of **freshwater** supply are faced by RO resulting in the need of an improved water management and by HU, due to increased water demand, that result in water shortage and further on threaten the present ecological status of waters and biodiversity.

4.3 Potentials reported from experts

Around 35 entries for potentials were mentioned by experts from target countries. The potentials are grouped into specific categories related to specific topics of bioeconomy. Table 23 gives an overview of the topics mentioned per country. Please note that this table shall only give an orientation of the topics of the potentials, but is not complete. For further details, it is referred to the Annex 7.5.

Table 23: Topics related to potentials of bioeconomy implementation reported from experts

Topics	BG	CZ	GR	HU	PL	RO	RS	SI	SK
Agriculture	x				x	x	x		
Best practices					x				
Bioenergy					x	x			
Biomass potential			x		x		x		
Bio-waste	x								
Capacity building				x				x	
Challenge					x				
Collaboration	x			x			x		x
Demand			x						
Food					x				
Food waste				x					
Forestry	x								
Infrastructure			x						
Investment				x					
Legal framework							x		
Location					x				
RDI		x		x	x				
Society				x					

All experts have in common that bioeconomy has great potential in their countries. Potentials are seen in the sectors of food, agro, forestry and bioenergy, more specifically in organic farming, biogas and biomethane sectors as well as in collaborations and existing infrastructure.

Potentials mentioned by experts in the agricultural sector range from the **acquisition of new biomass** from abandoned land (BG), from abundant natural resources (GR) or from generally large agricultural areas (RS). Also, the conversion from biological waste and residues into valuable resources is reported as a potential source for biomass (BG). In the forestry sector, also great potential was reported from BG, RO, RS. High potential in the food sector was reported from PL by promoting high quality food products and from RO. Food waste is another potential biomass source that was mentioned by HU experts.

Existing **infrastructure** and expertise for the bioeconomy implementation was reported from GR. From the location point of view, Greece has a strategic **location** that can be an advantage for accessing European and international markets for bio-based products and services (GR) and also Poland reported that potential for the transfer of biomass and biproducts also by providing storage space (PL). There is a growing demand for sustainable products and services worldwide, which can create opportunities for Greek businesses to tap into this market by developing innovative bio-based products and solutions (GR). Furthermore, investment to increase energy efficiency was reported by HU.

There is further potential to increase **capacity** on knowledge for fund application (HU), interconnection between research and investors (HU) and on industry experts (SI). Collaborations should be strengthened to promote the bioeconomy concepts and to foster knowledge transfer (RS), encourage using good practices (BG, PL) as well as to use local solutions to tackle energy crisis (HU). This can be done among others via Action Plan discussions (HU), networking events (HU), bioeconomy clusters (RO) or by using existing circular economy networks (RS) and also by improving access to funding so that that private actors can collaborate with research, academia and transfer scientific knowledge to practice (SK). Developed R & D infrastructure and human resources have great potential to contribute to a successful implementation, to strengthen cooperation and to develop innovative solutions (PL).

Other potentials are seen in RS as Serbia is a candidate country in the EU and need to align its legislation and policies to EU and widening bioeconomy network among young people (HU).

4.4 Potentials reported in BIOEAST concept papers

Around 71 entries for potentials were extracted from BIOEAST concept papers. The potentials are grouped into specific categories related to specific topics of bioeconomy. Table 24 gives an overview of the topics mentioned per country. Please note that this

table shall only give an orientation of the topics of the potentials, but is not complete. For further details, it is referred to the Annex 7.5.

Table 24: Topics related to potentials of bioeconomy implementation reported in BIOEAST concept papers

Category	BG	CZ	EE	HR	HU	LT	LV	PL	RO	SI	SK
Agriculture	x		x	x			x	x	x	x	x
Agriculture and forestry								x			x
Bio-based industry		x						x			x
Biochemical industry	x										
Bioenergy				x		x					
Biomass potential					x	x		x	x	x	x
Biorefineries					x						
Biotechnology		x									
Collaboration						x					
Food system and industry	x	x		x	x						x
Forestry							x				
Governance & Policy	x		x	x	x	x	x				
Infrastructure						x					
RDI			x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
Technology						x				x	
Transport											x
Wood & wood products	x		x			x	x			x	
Awareness											x
Digitalization											x
Low labour productivity								x			
Valorisation								x			
Ecosystems					x						
Public health											x
Fisheries							x				
Demand						x					

Potentials that have been revealed in the BIOEAST concept papers are situated largely in the **agricultural** sector as an important source of biomass (Romania has one of the largest agri-food industry sector on Europe, Poland has the largest utilised agricultural area and number of farms), but also in the development of the organic farming sector (PL) and the production of organic products (RO), as well as organic fertilizers through the transformation of biological waste to biomass (SK, HU). Livestock excrements are other potential sources that can be used for its energy content (biogas production) and nutrient content (digestate utilization) (SI). Furthermore, the cultivation of aromatic plants and essential oils were pointed out for Bulgaria having a well-established technologies & sufficient capacity of the distillation facilities and organic solvent extraction. The modernization of the primary sector and the improvement of resource

efficiency was reported in CZ. Current low levels of resource productivity in agriculture (e.g. in PL) need to be explored.

Another high biomass potential has definitely the **forestry** sector with Poland having the largest area of wooded land and growing stock. In HR sustainable forest management has been already contracted at the existing and pending solid biomass cogeneration plants for the next 5 to 14 years. Wood is the most promising source of raw materials for many countries (e.g., SI, BG, LT).

Many countries reported an untapped potential in agricultural production and forestry (e.g. SI, PL). In fact, it is the most important and relevant asset for the development of bioeconomy. Further untapped potential for biomass was reported for the sustainable use of domestic resources (SK), organic waste management (PL), generally the provision of supply-side sectors to demand-side sectors (PL).

Additionally, there is an untapped potential for key enabling **technology** and smart specialisations to promote transformation to a bio-based industry (PL). Also, biomass production is often connected with poorly-valorised side-streams. An integration of technology into those sectors could stipulate performance (SI). Circular technological solutions and business models are needed (LT).

Agroforestry is mentioned in SK as having great potential as it can benefit the microclimate, water regime and biodiversity.

Huge potential is envisaged in the **industry** in SK which can help in the implementation of new technologies, bio-based materials and innovations. The **chemical industry** belongs to the "novel" bioeconomy-related sectors having great potential in BG with a leading sector in the manufacture and export of chemical products, phosphorus and nitrogen fertilizers and medicinal products. Together with active knowledge and innovations this can allow a rapid transition to bio-based production (BG).

Biogas production was detected as a relevant area in bioeconomy with great potential (PL, RO, LT). In LT the biogas production equipment industry is growing (biogas power plants, biogas purification). The use of **digestate** as a valuable material was pointed out (EE),

Biorefinery has already been demonstrated in HU for the processing of green biomass (e.g., grasses) to produce proteins for feed and fibre fractions for soil enhancers or for producing biogas.

The **food** sector is further very promising including the provision of healthy food and changing eating habits, e.g. in BG, CZ, SK, HR, HU, EE. The production of animal protein for food was seen as a great potential, e.g. from fish farming (EE). The food, beverages and tobacco products industries is one of the most highly developed branches in BG and can therefore have great potential in the transition, ranging from sustainable food production including the provision of healthy and organic food, the use of by-products

and the reduction of food loss and waste. Also, industrial digitalisation is seen as a right toll to overcome efficiency problems (HU). Digitalization is also mentioned to help with the development of materials and technologies as well as to improve the quality of life of citizens in the transformation (SK).

Policies and Governance show also potentials: Ministerial involvement as one of the prominent assets (HR, HU), but also programmes or other instruments can foster bioeconomy such as the “zero waste” path which could accelerated biomethane production in biogas plants (PL). Policy commitment and availability of public funding are defined as relevant assets, too (LT).

Estonia was showing the highest growth in **liquid biofuels** industry compared to other BIOEAST countries. Biofuels is also seen in RO as having a full potential.

Another project in HU aimed the partial processing of **algae** to obtain proteins, fats, and carbohydrate components for food, feed, and fuel production.

Research, Development and Innovations (RDI) are identified as further potentials, as they can encourage cooperation and increase collaboration in fields such as networks, investments, technological solutions (PL, RO, SI, HR, EE, LV) both in novel sectors (PL) and in existing industry (SI). RDI can be regarded as a strong catalytic role in unlocking the bioeconomy potential (SI). It is growing, but still not at the highest level (RO).

Supportive is the **increasing awareness** of citizens on sustainable solutions, land management, biomass use and healthy lifestyles that can trigger the bioeconomy implementation (SK). The demand for biological materials is rising and so there is a rapid growth in various bioeconomy fields (LT).

Valorisation is seen as potential to allow product and services that have a higher price to be valued more favourably (PL).

5. Conclusions on the initial situation in CEE2ACT target countries

The overall objective of the CEE2ACT project is to empower the target 10 CEE2ACT countries (BG, CZ, GR, HR, HU, PL, RO, RS, SK and SI) to develop bioeconomy strategies and action plans through knowledge transfer and the adoption of innovative governance models from experienced countries - countries with a more advanced bioeconomy policy - (AT, BE, FI, DE, ES, SE, NL). Experience has shown that one cannot simply transfer working concepts from one country to another. It is important to know the framework conditions of the target countries in order to find optimal solutions. For this reason, following the first specific objective of CEE2ACT (SO1), this inventory attempts to provide a clear picture of the current state of play of the development of the implementation of circular bioeconomy and circular bioeconomy strategies in the CEE2ACT target countries.

To show the status quo in the target countries extended inventories of the implementation of bioeconomy strategies but also on socio-economic and environmental framework have been provided. On the other hand, main challenges have been queried from target country partners ending in potentials reported from experts.

5.1 Prerequisites for the implementation of bioeconomy

To give an overview of the status of bioeconomy and policy development in target countries compared to contributing countries as well as Baltic States a detailed look into existing policy direction/initiatives/visions in each country has been made to identify which areas can be leveraged by the project. This inventory also shall help to show which aspects the project can help advance, in order to get the attention of national administrations.

The country comparison shows that, as expected, dedicated bioeconomy strategies are already in place in each of the CEE2ACT “contributing countries”. As well as in Latvia as the only Baltic states. These dedicated strategies are currently still missing in the target countries, although there are differences in the progress of the specific developments. The Visegrád countries (PL, CZ, SK, HU), together with the neighboring countries HR and LI (from the Baltic States) have already their dedicated strategies under development. Generally, all sectors related to bioeconomy are included in existing national strategies except for some country specific conditions.

In four (SI, RS, RO, BG) out of 10 target countries, there are so far only other related strategies and policies reported from experts.

Concerning other related strategies, it turned out that from the considered strategies and policies most (11 out of 13) have been implemented in PL and BG followed by HU

with 10 strategies. Other CEE2ACT target countries show a maximum of 7 strategies implemented with RO reporting only five strategies and HR experts only showing four strategies.

European strategies on Agriculture (CAP), Forestry, Energy and Climate (ENCP) as well as Circular Economy have been implemented in all target countries inclusive Serbia as EU candidate state. Other relevant strategies like the Industry Strategy, the biodiversity strategy or the strategy on rural development are only reported from five to eight countries and farm to fork strategy or environmental policy is only reported from three countries. The exception to this is the Blue Economy strategy, which primarily concerns countries with access to the sea, such as BG, GR, HR, PL, RO and SI but also here only two countries already have such a dedicated strategy in their countries (BG and SI) There is no specific structure to be recognized, the strategies implemented nationally seem not to follow a specific order.

These initial results show that the **political background** of the individual countries is already very different and that this must be taken into account when designing the bioeconomy strategy in each case. Particularly in the countries where implementation is not yet in the preliminary stages, more educational work must be done here and it is not enough to work on direct implementation, but the focus must also be placed there on the political implementation of the respective strategies.

In addition to the political preconditions for the implementation of the bioeconomy strategy in general and the implementation of specific measures to strengthen the bioeconomy specifically, the **economic framework conditions** are an essential factor. Here, a major difference between the CEE2ACT contributing countries and the target countries could be shown. With the exception of Hungary, which has a normalized GDP of 0.76, all target countries have an average GDP of 0.34 normalised to (NL which has been chosen as country of comparison as it has the highest GDP), which is far below the average GDP of 0.89 compared to NL for the contributing countries.

The contribution of the individual bioeconomy sectors to the total bioeconomy turnover of a country already shows differences with regard to wood, wood products and furniture but also, above all, in the area of agriculture, where the share is currently higher in the target countries than in the other partner countries. Forestry, on the other hand, is underrepresented, but this is also related to the natural conditions as mainly in target countries most of the biomass is produced within agriculture with the exception of Slovenia where, similar to some contributing countries, forestry biomass predominates.

Looking at the existing use of renewable energy the average share of renewable transport in the target countries is twice as high as in the Baltic States, and the share of renewable transport in the contributing countries is twice as high as in the target countries. However, the range of variation is large. The comparatively low shares in HR and SI are striking. The share of renewables for electricity over all countries is on average

31% across all CEE2ACT countries including Baltic states with the lowest share in Hungary (8%). From target countries HR and RO stand out with values above 50 %. However, it is also clear that the existence or absence of a renewable energy strategy is not the decisive factor for the use of renewable energies as no direct connection could be verified. But in any case, a great potential to **increase the share of bioenergy** can be recognized in many target countries.

In average the bio waste generated by households in contributing countries is almost three times higher than in target countries and also higher as in the Baltic. The recovery rate in contributing countries is accordingly also higher than in target countries. the **great potential of biowaste management** in all target countries could be demonstrated,

Biggest potential on arable land compared to the number of inhabitants can be seen in the Baltic Countries but also BG, HU and RO have more than 0.4 km² of arable land per inhabitant and therefore good framework conditions to use this potential in terms of bioeconomy.

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7. ANNEX

7.1 Data points extracted for each CEE2ACT country

Country	Economics										
	Turnover										
	All bioeconomy sectors	Agriculture (ø 21%; 10%/38%)	Bio-based chemicals and materials (ø 6%; 1%/19%)	Bio-based electricity (ø 1%; 0%/4%)	Bio-based textiles (ø 2%; 1%/5%)	Fishing and Aquaculture (ø 1%; 0%/3%)	Food, Beverage, Tobacco (ø 41%; 22%/58%)	Forestry (ø 5%; 0%/17%)	Liquid biofuels (ø 1%; 0%/2%)	Pulp & paper (ø 9%; 2%/3%)	Wood, wood products & furniture (ø 13%; 2%/35%)
AT	68.174	7.473	6.348	0.635	1.639	0.100	26.782	2.238	0.513	11.058	11.387
BE	89.832	10.293	17.353	0.673	1.392	0.134	49.907	0.407	0.942	4.483	4.247
DE	464.146	56.178	49.221	18.43	8.166	0.407	241.844	5.461	2.653	45.258	36.529
ES	235.713	55.413	12.816	0.48	5.879	2.669	131.551	1.786	1.158	14.022	9.938
FI	51.894	4.994	2.11	1.093	0.453	0.219	11.278	5.512	1.201	16.927	8.108
NL	131.792	32.271	6.495	n.a	1.556	0.509	76.596	0.35	0.592	8.067	5.355
SE	74.203	8.573	6.302	0.801	0.374	0.24	19.734	9.525	0.933	15.292	12.43
BG	14.737	4.303	0.581	0.106	0.776	0.072	6.842	0.407	0.085	0.704	0.863
CZ	38.276	9.023	2.883	n.a	1.099	0.071	15.554	1.941	n.a	3.42	4.285
GR	34.800	12.481	1.264	0.091	0.739	0.892	16.811	0.076	0.277	1.515	0.656
HU	31.941	10.171	2.797	0.171	0.516	0.041	13.926	0.585	0.287	1.907	1.542
HR	11.523	2.617	0.487	0.023	0.38	0.289	5.506	0.411	0	0.508	1.301
PL	146.878	28.86	4.149	0.563	2.731	0.173	77.645	3.648	0.922	11.182	16.936
RO	42.805	16.396	1.642	0.028	1.833	0.418	14.637	1.673	0.153	1.314	4.712
RS											
SI	8.077	1.405	1.035	0.022	0.4	0.015	2.535	0.515	0	0.958	1.193
SK	12.832	2.904	0.284	0.175	0.443	0.011	4.874	1.081	0.011	1.411	1.638
EE	7.585	1.004	0.042	0.177	0.178	0.101	2.115	1.069	0	0.245	2.655
LT	12.461	3.218	0.369	0.057	0.354	0.119	4.506	0.562	0.121	0.627	2.529
LV	8.037	1.747	0.173	0.095	0.107	0.083	2.025	1.399	0	0.123	2.285

Country	Economics						
	Inhabitants (2019)	Value added at factor costs (2019, in million €)	Value added at factor costs (2019, in million € per capita)	Employed people in total (in thousands, 2019)	Employed People in all bioeconomy sectors (in thousands, 2019)	Share of employed people total in bioeconomy	GDP total per country, year 2019 (€ billion)
AT	8,858,775	19,516	2.20	4,360	329	8%	397.1
BE	11,455,519	23,311	2.03	4,980	221	4%	478.6
DE	83,019,213	125,444	1.51	41,590	2,169	5%	3,472.6
ES	46,937,060	69,283	1.48	19,780	1,443	7%	1,245.3
FI	5,517,919	14,428	2.61	2,530	181	7%	239.8
NL	17,282,163	32,809	1.90	9,120	404	4%	812.9
SE	10,230,185	22,621	2.21	5,070	263	5%	476.8
BG	7,000,039	4,270	0.61		774		61.5
CZ	10,649,800	10,817	1.02	5,310	388	7%	225.6
GR	10,724,599	11,736	1.09	3,910	673	17%	183.3
HU	4,076,246	9,832	2.41	4,645	373	8%	146.5
HR	9,772,756	3,978	0.41		206		55.7
PL	37,972,812	36,649	0.97	19,780	2,369	12%	532.3
RO	19,414,458	14,650	0.75	5,165	2,308	45%	224.2
RS	6,963,764		-		-		46.0
SI	2,080,908	2,696	1.30	1,050	117	11%	48.5
SK	5,450,421	3,469	0.64	2,440	162	7%	94.4
EE	1,324,820	1,935	1.46	670	62	9%	27.8
LT	2,794,184	3,640	1.30	1,380	186	13%	48.9
LV	1,919,968	2,505	1.30	910	120	13%	30.7

Food and nutrition security										
Country	Inhabitants (2019)	Agricultural factor income per annual work (index, 2010=100)	Total biomass supply for food purposes, including inputs (kt (kilotonnes) dry matter)	Biomass directly consumed by EU citizens as food (kt (kilotonnes) dry matter)	Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population, yearly estimates (%)	Food purchasing power, food and non-alcoholic beverages (nominal expenditure as % of GDP (GDP=100))	Daily calorie supply per capita by animal products (kcal/cap/d)	Daily calorie supply per capita by vegetal products (kcal/cap/d)	Daily calorie supply per capita by animal products (%)	Daily calorie supply per capita by vegetal products (%)
AT	8,858,775.0	94.0	11,240.4	2,153.5	3.0	5.0	1,166.0	2,529.0	31.6	68.4
BE	11,455,519.0	95.3	14,448.0	2,837.9	3.7	6.2	1,147.0	2,622.0	30.4	69.6
DE	83,019,213.0	115.7	98,177.6	19,344.2	3.4	5.3	1,086.0	2,468.0	30.6	69.4
ES	46,937,060.0	128.3	44,139.9	9,892.5	8.8	7.4	857.0	2,465.0	25.8	74.2
FI	5,517,919.0	91.5	6,999.7	1,224.6	8.0	5.7	1,331.0	2,012.0	39.8	60.2
NL	17,282,163.0	94.7	19,903.9	3,652.7	4.7	4.9	1,155.0	2,142.0	35.0	65.0
SE	10,230,185.0	104.7	10,474.1	2,075.5	5.3	5.4	1,052.0	2,132.0	33.0	67.0
BG	7,000,039.0	242.6	6,277.8	1,317.4	13.2	11.5	703.0	2,151.0	24.6	75.4
CZ	10,649,800.0	148.8	11,355.1	2,301.1	4.2	7.2	924.0	2,352.0	28.2	71.8
GR	10,724,599.0	105.7	10,235.8	2,256.2	8.6	12.1	813.0	2,568.0	24.0	76.0
HR	4,076,246.0	131.8	4,406.4	827.7	11.0	13.0	928.0	2,146.0	30.2	69.8
HU	9,772,756.0	180.6	11,242.5	2,151.8	8.6	8.6	1,077.0	2,238.0	32.5	67.5
PL	37,972,812.0	154.6	46,087.3	8,597.3	5.8	9.4	1,016.0	2,521.0	28.7	71.3
RO	19,414,458.0	140.0	22,578.3	4,501.0	13.9	15.3	942.0	2,638.0	26.3	73.7
RS	6,963,764.0									
SI	2,080,908.0	121.0	2,116.7	415.0	8.2	7.7	815.0	2,377.0	25.5	74.5
SK	5,450,421.0	189.2	5,138.9	1,031.1	6.0	9.7	846.0	2,025.0	29.5	70.5
EE	1,324,820.0	108.7	1,521.8	274.7	7.9	9.5	1,144.0	2,104.0	35.2	64.8
LT	2,794,184.0	137.4	3,267.2	623.7	11.3	12.2	1,019.0	2,392.0	29.9	70.1
LV	1,919,968.0	169.9	2,066.3	402.4	10.2	10.5	1,029.0	2,200.0	31.9	68.1

Country	Managing Natural Resources Sustainably								
	Biomass production in EU from primary production systems AGRICULTURE (tonnes dry matter)	Biomass production in EU from primary production systems FISHERIES (tonnes dry matter)	Biomass production in EU from primary production systems FORESTRY (tonnes dry matter)	Agriculture (∅ 65%; 18%/94%)	Fisheries (∅ 0%; 0%/1%)	Forestry (∅ 35%; 6%/82%)	Biomass production in EU from primary production systems AGRICULTURE (kg dry matter/capita)	Biomass production in EU from primary production systems FISHERIES (kg dry matter/capita)	Biomass production in EU from primary production systems FORESTRY (kg dry matter/capita)
AT	11,333.9	1.0	9,237.0	0.6	0.0	0.4	1.3	0.0	1.0
BE	9,676.5	6.8	2,834.0	0.8	0.0	0.2	0.8	0.0	0.2
DE	113,774.7	78.3	34,436.0	0.8	0.0	0.2	1.4	0.0	0.4
ES	55,152.6	300.2	8,847.0	0.9	0.0	0.1	1.2	0.0	0.2
FI	7,205.0	51.8	33,104.0	0.2	0.0	0.8	1.3	0.0	6.0
NL	12,573.8	108.1	1,659.0	0.9	0.0	0.1	0.7	0.0	0.1
SE	14,186.3	55.3	38,796.0	0.3	0.0	0.7	1.4	0.0	3.8
BG	17,638.3	6.1	3,361.0	0.8	0.0	0.2	2.5	0.0	0.5
CZ	17,113.3	6.1	10,138.0	0.6	0.0	0.4	1.6	0.0	1.0
GR	13,831.9	50.1	861.0	0.9	0.0	0.1	1.3	0.0	0.1
HR	5,535.5	22.3	2,785.0	0.7	0.0	0.3	1.4	0.0	0.7
HU	24,133.0	5.3	2,990.0	0.9	0.0	0.1	2.5	0.0	0.3
PL	62,316.6	64.1	23,702.0	0.7	0.0	0.3	1.6	0.0	0.6
RO	50,583.6	6.3	7,600.0	0.9	0.0	0.1	2.6	0.0	0.4
RS							-	-	-
SI	1,959.0	0.6	2,362.0	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.9	0.0	1.1
SK	7,243.2	1.0	4,895.0	0.6	0.0	0.4	1.3	0.0	0.9
EE	2,463.8	19.2	6,007.0	0.3	0.0	0.7	1.9	0.0	4.5
LT	10,836.0	27.8	3,560.0	0.8	0.0	0.2	3.9	0.0	1.3
LV	5,114.0	28.8	6,753.0	0.4	0.0	0.6	2.7	0.0	3.5

Reducing Dependence on Non-renewable Unsustainable Resources												
Country	Energy productivity (€ per kg of oil equivalent) GLOSSAR	Share of renewable energy in gross final energy (%) (Scoreboard consumption)	Share of non-renewable energy	Total Biomass consumed for energy (kt dry matter)	Total Biomass consumed for materials (kt dry matter)	Total Biomass consumed for energy (% von total biomass)	For Energy	For Materials	Share of woody biomass used for energy (%) (Scoreboard ?)	Share of renewables for transport (%)	Share of renewables for electricity (%)	Share of renewables for heating & cooling (%)
AT	9.7	33.8	66.2	11,345.0	5,321.8	0.7	1,280.7	600.7	42.2	9.7	71.6	33.7
BE	6.5	9.9	90.1	2,842.3	2,804.9	0.5	248.1	244.8	39.0	6.6	17.3	8.1
DE	9.7	17.3	82.7	34,170.0	22,326.0	0.6	411.6	268.9	45.0	7.0	34.6	13.4
ES	8.9	17.9	82.2	5,458.0	5,929.7	0.5	116.3	126.3	37.3	5.8	36.3	17.7
FI	5.9	42.7	57.3	19,086.0	5,645.0	0.8	3,458.9	1,023.0	36.6	18.8	35.2	54.6
NL	8.3	8.9	91.1	2,017.0	3,333.8	0.4	116.7	192.9	80.7	6.0	13.8	5.7
SE	8.8	55.8	44.2	20,999.0	7,592.0	0.7	2,052.7	742.1	33.4	26.8	65.9	65.8
BG	2.4	21.6	78.5	2,301.4	830.2	0.7	328.8	118.6	49.5	7.3	19.0	29.9
CZ	4.6	16.2	83.8	6,231.5	1,972.5	0.8	585.1	185.2	49.1	6.6	13.7	19.7
GR	7.3	19.6	80.4	464.0	984.7	0.3	43.3	91.8	53.4	4.0	24.5	28.3
HR	5.9	28.5	71.5	1,581.1	163.0	0.9	387.9	40.0	44.6	1.2	46.4	36.6
HU	4.9	12.6	87.4	3,184.0	1,451.1	0.7	325.8	148.5	54.3	7.7	7.5	19.9
PL	4.7	15.4	84.6	10,852.6	12,261.2	0.5	285.8	322.9	38.9	4.2	13.1	14.9
RO	5.3	24.3	75.7	12,983.0	3,815.5	0.8	668.7	196.5	56.5	6.6	42.0	26.6
RS			100.0			#DIV/0!	-	-				
SI	6.3	22.0	78.0	1,240.0	906.0	0.6	595.9	435.4	53.5	2.6	32.4	34.6
SK	5.1	16.9	83.1	2,357.3	1,516.0	0.6	432.5	278.1	34.9	7.0	21.3	9.8
EE	4.1	31.7	68.3	2,493.0	1,393.0	0.6	1,881.8	1,051.5	38.8	0.4	17.0	51.7
LT	4.9	25.5	74.5	2,986.4	1,549.2	0.7	1,068.8	554.4	56.5	4.3	18.3	46.5
LV	4.9	40.9	59.1	4,183.0	173.1	1.0	2,178.7	90.2	38.8	2.3	54.4	54.6

Country	Biowaste				Managing Natural Resources		
	Biowaste GENERATED by households (kg/capita)	Biowaste RECOVERED by households (kg/capita)	Biowaste GENERATED by Industry and Agriculture (kg/capita)	Biowaste RECOVERED by Industry and Agriculture (kg/capita)	Biochemical oxygen demand in rivers (mg O2/l)	Phosphate in rivers (mg PO4/l)	Nitrate in groundwater (mgNO3/l)
AT	192.6	157.2	272.4	259.2	1.7	0.0	21.9
BE	146.7	800.9	143.9	784.8	2.7	0.2	30.6
DE	166.5	180.5	165.8	180.1	n.a	0.1	27.6
ES	137.1	118.8	48.6	111.3	n.a	n.a	n.a
FI	126.4	735.0	125.5	733.4	n.a	0.0	n.a
NL	160.0	476.4	158.5	470.6	n.a	n.a	n.a
SE	144.0	77.2	143.8	77.2	n.a	0.0	n.a
BG	133.4	90.0	57.4	57.2	2.3	0.1	29.8
CZ	-	-	-	-	2.6	0.1	18.0
GR	-	-	-	-	n.a	n.a	n.a
HR	88.1	115.9	19.9	99.1	1.9	0.0	n.a
HU	78.4	97.4	26.8	92.3	n.a	n.a	n.a
PL	68.4	128.1	38.9	120.1	3.0	n.a	n.a
RO	58.7	178.0	8.8	157.4	3.5	0.1	n.a
RS	-	-	-	-	n.a	n.a	n.a
SI	91.5	132.5	56.7	123.5	0.9	0.0	18.3
SK	106.9	132.5	42.9	130.0	2.2	0.1	14.4
EE	75.1	223.1	65.5	215.2	1.5	0.0	5.1
LT	94.9	151.9	36.6	142.4	2.4	0.1	n.a
LV	86.2	91.2	43.1	76.6	1.3	0.1	n.a

Agriculture / Cultivation and harvest of fruits and vegetables										
Country	arable land (% of land area)	arable land (ha)	arable land km ² /EW	Crop yield - wheat and spelt (1000t)	Crop yield - wheat and spelt (1000ha)	Crop yield - grain maize and corn-cob-mix (1000t)	Crop yield - grain maize and corn-cob-mix (1000ha)	Crop yield - barley (1000t)	Crop yield - barley (1000ha)	Share of organic farming in utilised agricultural area %
AT	0.2	1,325,530.0	0.1	1,606.2	278.3	2,298.9	220.7	833.0	137.2	0.3
BE	0.3	857,286.0	0.1	1,895.8	203.8	529.6	48.6	397.4	46.8	0.1
DE	0.3	11,714,000.0	0.1	23,062.6	3,118.1	3,664.8	416.0	11,591.5	1,708.8	0.1
ES	0.2	11,812,314.6	0.3	5,801.0	1,920.1	4,184.5	356.8	7,400.0	2,693.5	0.1
FI	0.1	2,245,000.0	0.4	901.6	197.6	-	-	1,682.4	397.9	0.1
NL	0.3	1,011,100.0	0.1	1,137.8	120.6	185.4	19.0	243.2	33.4	0.0
SE	0.1	2,540,120.0	0.2	3,476.8	469.5	11.3	1.6	1,546.5	291.8	0.2
BG	0.3	3,476,000.0	0.5	6,162.0	1,198.7	3,990.2	560.9	547.2	112.0	0.0
CZ	0.3	2,484,472.0	0.2	4,812.2	839.5	620.3	74.8	1,718.1	319.6	0.2
GR	0.2	2,131,930.4	0.2	979.2	350.5	1,233.6	115.5	366.6	132.6	0.1
HR	0.1	823,000.0	0.2	794.0	143.2	2,298.3	255.9	275.4	53.7	0.1
HU	0.5	4,317,000.0	0.4	5,377.7	1,015.6	8,277.8	1,027.6	1,383.3	247.4	0.1
PL	0.4	11,055,000.0	0.3	11,012.4	2,511.3	3,734.0	665.0	3,374.4	975.3	0.0
RO	0.4	8,966,000.0	0.5	10,297.1	2,168.4	17,432.2	2,681.9	1,880.0	448.9	0.0
RS	0.3	2,579,000.0	0.4	2,534.6	577.5	7,344.5	962.1	373.3	100.1	-
SI	0.1	181,230.0	0.1	139.8	26.7	360.4	38.9	102.5	21.1	0.1
SK	0.3	1,349,000.0	0.2	1,939.1	406.8	1,444.8	197.2	599.6	126.4	0.1
EE	0.2	690,000.0	0.5	846.6	167.0	-	-	523.1	123.4	0.2
LT	0.4	2,211,900.0	0.8	3,843.9	895.8	98.0	12.8	588.5	174.8	0.1
LV	0.2	1,319,000.0	0.7	2,371.0	492.7	-	-	305.4	86.8	0.1

Country	Forest-based sector									
	forest area (% of land area)	forest area (km ²)	Forest area km ² /1000EW	Forest and other wooded land growing stock - growing stock of forests (1000 m ³)	Forest and other wooded land growing stock - growing stock of other wooden land (1000 m ³)	Forest and other wooded land growing stock - total per forest area (1000m ³ /km ²)	Ratio of annual fellings (m ³ /ha/year) to net annual increment (m ³ /ha/year)	Biomass production in EU from primary production sectors: Forestry (Tonnes of dry matter)	Roundwood removals - overbark (m ³)	Roundwood removals - underbark (m ³)
AT	0.5	38,955.6	4.4	1,162,000.0	n.a	29.8	0.7	9,237.0	21,506,897.1	18,903,715.0
BE	0.2	6,893.0	0.6	n.a	n.a	-	1.0	2,834.0	5,933,743.0	5,212,140.0
DE	0.3	114,190.0	1.4	3,663,000.0	-	32.1	0.9	34,436.0	88,616,989.6	77,820,994.0
ES	0.4	185,678.8	4.0	1,108,200.0	n.a	6.0	0.5	8,847.0	19,355,879.6	17,020,157.0
FI	0.7	224,090.0	40.6	2,448,850.0	n.a	10.9	0.8	33,104.0	72,404,837.5	63,666,864.0
NL	0.1	3,685.7	0.2	81,990.0	-	22.2	0.6	1,659.0	3,510,871.2	3,067,700.0
SE	0.7	279,800.0	27.4	3,618,650.0	20,570.0	13.0	0.8	38,796.0	84,580,721.0	74,400,000.0
BG	0.4	38,800.0	5.5	748,840.0	n.a	19.3	0.8	3,361.0	7,030,493.2	6,163,699.0
CZ	0.3	26,752.8	2.5	786,470.0	n.a	29.4	0.8	10,138.0	7,030,493.2	6,163,699.0
GR	0.3	39,018.0	3.6	191,830.0	n.a	4.9	0.2	861.0	1,555,781.1	1,359,105.0
HR	0.3	19,366.1	4.8	425,140.0	6,320.0	22.3	0.7	2,785.0	6,164,572.6	5,400,097.0
HU	0.2	20,544.7	2.1	393,100.0	n.a	19.1	0.9	2,990.0	6,369,460.6	5,575,423.0
PL	0.3	94,710.0	2.5	2,694,000.0	n.a	28.4	0.8	23,702.0	49,201,595.4	43,267,933.0
RO	0.3	69,290.5	3.6	2,354,790.0	790.0	34.0	0.8	7,600.0	18,046,521.5	15,827,246.0
RS	0.3	27,222.2	3.9	n.a	n.a	-				
SI	0.6	12,398.6	6.0	413,110.0	1,000.0	33.4	0.7	2,362.0	5,260,578.8	4,618,159.0
SK	0.4	19,259.0	3.5	537,670.0	n.a	27.9	0.7	4,895.0	10,181,804.7	8,956,874.0
EE	0.6	24,384.0	18.4	494,150.0	3,980.0	20.4	0.9	6,007.0	12,521,744.0	10,986,970.0
LT	0.4	22,000.0	7.9	555,600.0	2,150.0	25.4	0.9	3,560.0	7,616,170.3	6,688,000.0
LV	0.5	34,069.2	17.7	669,080.0	2,470.0	19.7	0.9	6,753.0	16,873,101.6	14,822,065.0

7.2 Survey among CEE2ACT experts in target countries

TEMPLATE for Task 2.1

Version 21.04.2023

Established by BOKU, IUNG

Aim of this template: This template shall help to gather country specific information that is not covered in published reports or dashboards, such as the EU Bioeconomy Country and Monitoring System Dashboard

Target group: CEE2ACT countries, whose national bioeconomy strategy is currently in implementation (see below)

Request: Please fill in questions Q1-5 in the datasheet for your country and return the file to BOKU and IUNG until 5th May 2023

Corresponding deliverables: Gathered information will be processed and published in the following CEE2ACT deliverable:
 D2.1 Baseline assessment report on bioeconomy implementation and policy development in CEE2ACT target countries

Components of the D2.1:	
	Definition of bioeconomy incl. System boundaries
	Status of bioeconomy implementation in CEE2ACT countries:
	* Bioeconomy POLICY LANDSCAPE
	* Bioeconomy INFRASTRUCTURE
	* Bioeconomy ECOSYSTEM CONDITIONS
	* Bioeconomy INITIATIVES
	* Challenges and Potentials of bioeconomy implementation
Information sources:	
	* EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System Dashboard incl. JRC Reports
	* EU Bioeconomy Country Dashboard incl. JRC Reports
	* EUROSTAT, Worldbank and other data sources
	* BIOEASTup concept papers
	Additional information from CEE2ACT partners (strategies under development)

Funded by the European Union

HR Croatia																																																																																						
Please fill in all light orange areas in this questionnaire! Feel free to comment or describe in other cells!																																																																																						
Q1	<p>Implementation status of your National Bioeconomy Strategy:</p> <p>Note that this is the information mentioned in the EU Bioeconomy Country Dashboard for your country</p> <p>Link to the EU Bioeconomy Country Dashboard Under development</p>																																																																																					
Q1a	<p>Do you agree with the above mentioned status in the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System Dashboard?</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Yes/No</p>																																																																																					
Q1b	<p>Please explain why or why not:</p>																																																																																					
Q2	<p>Has a draft version or any other form of document for your National Bioeconomy Strategy already been published?</p> <p>If YES, continue with Q2. If NO, continue with Q3.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Yes/No</p>																																																																																					
Q2a	<p>Do you know which SECTORS are covered/are pinpointed in the national strategy under development?</p> <p>Please tick the sectors mentioned in the current version of the national strategy.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #f4a460;">Sectors</th> <th style="background-color: #f4a460;">Please tick sectors that are covered (x)</th> <th style="background-color: #f4a460;">Please tick sectors that are pinpointed (x)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>Agriculture</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Forestry</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Fisheries</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Aquaculture</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Organic waste</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Food</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Wood, wood products & furniture</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Pulp & paper</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Biotechnology</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Bio-based textiles</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Bio-base chemicals and materials</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Bioenergy (incl. Transport biofuels)</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Ecosystem services</td><td></td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>Other specific sectors:</td><td></td><td></td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Sectors	Please tick sectors that are covered (x)	Please tick sectors that are pinpointed (x)	Agriculture			Forestry			Fisheries			Aquaculture			Organic waste			Food			Wood, wood products & furniture			Pulp & paper			Biotechnology			Bio-based textiles			Bio-base chemicals and materials			Bioenergy (incl. Transport biofuels)			Ecosystem services			Other specific sectors:																																										
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Q3.	<p>Which EU policies and programs related to bioeconomy are already implemented in your country?</p> <p>Please conduct a short desktop research, if those policies and programs are implemented in your countries and how. Please use the provided link to see the title of the strategy in your language, that might help to find the implementation status of the specific EU strategy in your country.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #f4a460;">EU policies and programs</th> <th style="background-color: #f4a460;">Link</th> <th style="background-color: #f4a460;">Implementation STATUS (in preparation, under review, in force, unknown status)</th> <th style="background-color: #f4a460;">Implementation MODE (eg, strategy, action plan, law)</th> <th style="background-color: #f4a460;">Title, link</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td colspan="5">Bioeconomy Strategy related policies:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Common Agricultural Policy</td> <td>https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/com-mon-agricultural-policy/cap-2023-27_en</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Forest Strategy</td> <td>COM/2021/2572 final. 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BG	Уъркшоп на тема „Представяне на концепция за стратегия за научни изследвания и иновации в биоикономиката при Аграрен университет-Пловдив“	Workshop on the topic "Presentation of a concept for a strategy for scientific research and innovation in the bioeconomy at the Agricultural University - Plovdiv"	https://www.auplovdiv.bg/%D0%BD%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%B8/workshop-capbio4bg
BG	Проучване на потенциала на биоикономиката в България	Study of the potential of the bioeconomy in Bulgaria	https://celebio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/CELEBio_D4.4_National-Bioeconomy-Dossier_-BG.pdf
BG	среща в Аграрен университет Пловдив регионален хъб за биоикономика- Пловдив	meeting at Agricultural University Plovdiv regional hub for bioeconomy - Plovdiv	https://capbio4.bg/html/?go=news&p=detail&newsId=522
BG	Мисия Зелена България	Mission Green Bulgaria	https://move.bg/wp-content/uploads/Doklad-Misiya-Zelena-Blgariya-MOVE.BG-WWF-Grijnpijs-IKI-yuli-2022.pdf
BG	Онлайн уъркшоп на тема „Преходът към биоикономика“	Online workshop "The transition to the bioeconomy"	https://www.sme.government.bg/?p=59092
BG	Онлайн уъркшоп на тема „Биоикономика: Насърчаване на взаимодействието между селските и градските региони“	Online workshop "Bioeconomy: Promoting interaction between rural and urban regions"	https://www.sme.government.bg/?p=58956
BG	АГРАРЕН УНИВЕРСИТЕТ – ПЛОВДИВ ПРЕДСТАВИ УСПЕШНИ ЕВРОПЕЙСКИ ПРИМЕРИ В БИОИКОНОМИКАТА	AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY - PLOVDIV PRESENTED SUCCESSFUL EUROPEAN EXAMPLES IN THE BIOECONOMY	https://www.auplovdiv.bg/%D0%BD%D0%B0%D1%83%D0%BA%D0%B0/%D1%80%D0%B5%D0%B3%D0%B8%D1%81%D1%82%D1%8A%D1%80-%D0%BD%D0%B0-%D0%B2%D1%8A%D0%BD%D1%88%D0%BD%D0%B8-%D0%BF%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B5%D0%BA%D1%82%D0%B8-%D0%B7%D0%B0-%D0%B0%D1%83/%D0%BC%D0%B5%D0%B6%D0%B4%D1%83%D0%BD%D0%B0%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B4%D0%BD%D0%B8-%D0%BF%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%B5%D0%BA%D1%82%D0%B8-1/coopid-ce-fnr-15-2020
BG	Семинар „Възможности за развитие на биоикономиката в България: проекти и програми на Аграрен университет- Пловдив“	Seminar "Possibilities for the development of the bioeconomy in Bulgaria: projects and programs of the Agricultural University - Plovdiv"	https://agro.bg/novini/liubopitno/seminar-vazmozhnosti-za-razvitie-na-bioikononikata-v-balgariya--proekti-i-programi-na-agraren-universitet--plovdiv/
BG	Онлайн семинар "Прилагане на земеделски практики за кръгова биоикономика в стопанствата"	Online seminar "Application of agricultural practices for circular bioeconomy in farms"	https://www.naas.government.bg/predstoyashi/informacionno-obuchitelni-seminari/onlajn-seminar-prilagane-na-zemedelski-stopanstvata

			praktiki-za-krigova-bioikonomika-v-stopanstvata
BG	Успешен пример в областта на биоикономиката	A successful example in the field of bioeconomy	https://agri.bg/novini/fermer-predstavi-novatsii-v-otplenieto-i-napoyavaneto-na-oranzheriyata
BG	Годишна работна среща по Националната научна програма „Здравословни храни за силна биоикономика и качество на живот“ (ННП-ХРАНИ) към Министерството на образованието и науката	Annual working meeting of the National Scientific Program "Healthy Foods for a Strong Bioeconomy and Quality of Life" (NNP-FOOD) at the Ministry of Education and Science	https://www.iae-bg.com/%D0%B7%D0%B4%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B2%D0%BE%D1%81%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%BD%D0%B8-%D1%85%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B8-%D0%B8-%D1%81%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BD%D0%B0-%D0%B1%D0%B8%D0%BE%D0%B8%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%BD%D0%BE%D0%BC/
BG	Анализ и профил на състоянието и потенциала за регионална биоикономика	Analysis and profile of the state and potential of a regional bioeconomy	https://www.iki.bas.bg/analiz-i-profil-na-sastoiianieto-i-potenciala-za-regionalna-bioikonomika
CZ	Platforma pro bioekonomiku ČR	Bioeconomy Platform CZ	https://bioeconomy.czu.cz/en
CZ	Jihočeský spolek pro bioekonomiku, z.s.	South Bohemian Association for Bioeconomy	https://bei.jcu.cz/h2020-projekt-power4bio-files/jihocesky-spolek-pro-bioekonomiku-jsbe-zakladni-udaje
EL	Ελληνικό Φόρουμ Βιοοικονομίας	Greek Bioeconomy Forum	https://www.facebook.com/people/Greek-Bioeconomy-Forum/100064660426838/?paipv=0&eav=AfbDszlg152S27nvNnhJisXVsl_iBf_TP_E94-qS5EDKQQWWp_G6r2qtfOahuiMso&rdr
EL	Κέντρο Βιώσιμης και Κυκλικής Βιοοικονομίας	Center for Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy and Energy	https://bioeconomy.aegean.gr/en
EL	Επιστημονικό Κέντρο Βιώσιμης Ανάπτυξης	Scientific Center for Sustainable Development	https://qualitynetfoundation.org/en/scientific-center-for-sustainable-development/
EL	Ινστιτούτο Βιο-Οικονομίας και Αγρο-Τεχνολογίας	Institute for Bio-Economy and Agri-Technology (iBO)	https://ibo.certh.gr/
HR			
HU	BIOEAST	BIOEAST	bioeast.eu
HU	Hungarian Bioeconomy Cluster	Hungarian Bioeconomy Cluster	https://www.bayzoltan.hu/en/company-management/hungarian-bioeconomy-cluster/
HU	Circular Hungary	https://circularhungary.hu/	info@circularhungary.hu
PL	AgroBioCluster	AgroBioCluster	http://agrobiocluster.pl/?lang=en

PL	The Stakeholder Platform BIOEASTsUP	The Stakeholder Platform BIOEASTsUP	https://bioeast.eu/description/
PL	Platforma Biogospodarki IUNG	Bioeconomy Platform	http://platforma.biogospodarka.iung.pl/en/
PL	Platforma Współpracy Biogospodarki zielona chemia	Chemical Cluster "Green Chemistry"	https://zielonachemia.eu/platforma-wspolpracy-biogospodarki/
PL	Stowarzyszenie Klaster Biogospodarki	Polish Technology Platform of Bioeconomy	http://klasterbio.pl/en/
PL	Polskie Stowarzyszenie Zrównoważonego Rolnictwa i Żywności	Polish Association of Sustainable Agriculture and Food	https://rolnictwozrownowazone.pl/
PL	Polska Ekologia	Chemical Cluster "Green Chemistry"	https://www.polskaekologia.org/

PL	Klaster Lifescience Kraków	Lifescience Cluster Cracow	https://lifescience.pl/
PL	NUTRIBIOMED Klaster	NUTRIBIOMED Cluster	http://nutribiomed.pl/
PL	Wschodni Klaster ICT	Eastern ICT Cluster	http://ecict.eu/en/home/
PL	Klaster Gospodarki Odpadowej i Recyklingu	Waste Management and Recycling Cluster - National Key Cluster	https://klasterodpadowy.com/portals/english
PL	Porozumienie o współpracy na rzecz rozwoju sektora biogazu i biometanu	Cooperation agreement for the development of the biogas and biomethane sector	<p>1. https://tge.pl/tge-news-read?cmn_id=91329&title=TGE+signs+the+Cooperation+Agreement+for+the+Development+of+the+Biogas+and+Biomethane+Sector</p> <p>2. https://www.gov.pl/web/klimat/podpisano-porozumienie-o-wspolpracy-na-rzecz-rozwoju-sektora-biogazu-i-biometanu</p>
PL	Inicjatywa "Zespół ds. Rozwoju Biogospodarki"	The 'Bioeconomy Development Team' initiative	<p>1. https://www.gov.pl/web/rozwoj-technologie/zespol-ds-rozwoju-biogospodarki</p>

RO	NA	BIOEAST Initiative's National Contact Point (NCP)	LINK
RO	NA	ASIMCOV Innovation Hub (BE-Rural Romania)	LINK
RO	NA	AGROFOOD Regional Innovative Circular economy Cluster	
RO	NA	AgroTransilvania Cluster	LINK
RO		ROCESP Romanian Circular Economy Stateholders Platform	LINK
RO	NA	BIORURAL Romania	LINK
RO	NA	RuralbioUP Romania	LINK
RO	NA	Green Energy Biomass Cluster	LINK
RO	NA	RoHealth The Health and Bioeconomy Cluster	LINK
RO	FNGAL	FLAG	LINK
RO	NRDN	RNDR	LINK
RO	NA	ProWood Cluster	LINK
RO	NA	ASFOR - Foresters Association	LINK
RO	NA	CLUSTERO - RO Clusters Association	LINK
RO	NA	IND-AGRO-POL	
RO	NA	Cluster BioDanubius	LINK
RO	NA	CFRO - RO Farmers Club	LINK
RO	NA	Inter-Bio	LINK
SR	Udruženje "Klaster Bioekonomija"	Association „Cluster Bioeconomy“ Subotica, Serbia	Goran Vasić, website under construction
SR	Privredna komora Srbije - Centar za cirkularnu ekonomiju	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia - Center for circular economy	Siniša Mitrović, Ivana Putnik https://pks.rs/udruzenje/sluzba-za-cirkularnu-ekonomiju
SR	Regionalna Agencija za razvoj malih i srednjih preduzeća Alma Mons d.o.o., Novi Sad	Regional agency for the development of small and medium size enterprises Alma Mons d.o.o., Novi Sad	Milica Vračević http://almamons.rs/
SR	Ministarstvo zaštite životne sredine republike Srbije - Grupa za cirkularnu i zelenu ekonomiju	Ministry of Environmental Protection of the Republic of Serbia - Group for the circular and green economy	Aleksandra Vučinić https://www.ekologija.gov.rs/lat
SR	Ministarstvo poljoprivrede, šumarstva i vodoprivrede	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Serbia	http://www.minpolj.gov.rs/?script=lat
SK	Bioeconomy Cluster	Bioeconomy Cluster	https://bioeconomy.sk/
SK	Združenie pre výrobu a využitie biopalív	Association for the Biofuel Production and Utilization	https://www.zvzb.sk/
SK	Združenie mladých farmárov	Association of Young Farmers	http://mladyfarmer.asyf.sk/
SK	Slovenská poľnohospodárska a potravinárska komora	Slovak Agriculture and Food Chamber	https://www.sppk.sk/
SK	Centrum pre trvaloudržateľné alternatívy	Center for Sustainable Alternatives	https://cepta.sk/
SK	Zväz spracovateľov dreva	Wood Processors Association	https://www.zsdsr.sk/

SK	Slovenský plastikársky klaster	Slovak Plastic Cluster	https://portal.spklaster.sk/index.php/en/
SK	HEMP Cluster	HEMP Cluster	https://www.hempcluster.eu/
SK	REPRIK	Regional industry innovation cluster Rimavská kotlina	https://www.repriku.eu/
SI	Strategija za bio-krožno gospodarstvo	Circular bioeconomy strategy	https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/ Contact person: Igor Kos
SI	SRIP Krožno gospodarstvo	Strategic Research and Innovation Partnership Circular economy	https://srip-circular-economy.eu/ Contact person: Nina Meglič
SI	Deep Demonstration in Slovenia	Deep Demonstration in Slovenia	https://www.climate-kic.org/circularslovenia-2/ Contact person: Bart Stegeman
SI	Value Chain Generator	Value Chain Generator	www.vcg.ai Contact person: Jon Goriup Dermastia
SI	WoodChainManager	WoodChainManager	https://wcm.gozdis.si/en/about-us/
SI	EIT FOOD Hub for Slovenia	EIT FOOD Hub for Slovenia	https://www.eitfood.eu/in-your-area/slovenia Contact person: Aleš Kuhar
SI	SRIP Hrana	Strategic Research and Innovation Partnership FOOD	https://www.gzs.si/srip-hrana/vsebina/English/About-SRIP-HRANA
SI	TBMCE 2023 6. mednarodna konferenca tehnologije in poslovni modeli za krožno gospodarstvo	TBMCE 2023 6th International Conference Technologies and Business Models for Circular Economy	
SI	H2GreenTECH Vodikov center	Project H2GreenTECH HYDROGEN CENTER	https://srip-circular-economy.eu/hydrogen-center/
SI	Alps4GreenC - Biochar potential in the region	Alps4GreenC - Biochar potential in the region	https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/alps4greenc/
SI		Roadmap towards circular economy in Slovenia	https://www.circularchange.com/projects-1/2018/11/8/roadmap-towards-the-circular-economy-in-slovenia
SI		Whey2Value technology to convert acid waste whey	http://www.whey2value.com/
SI		Collaboration between Melamin company and Jožef Štefan Institute on Bio-based melamine bio-polymer	https://srip-circular-economy.eu/project/the-development-of-melamine-bio-polymers-for-coatings/

7.4 Challenges

Reported challenges sorted by key words and country

Country	Key words	Short description	Reference
BG	Biochemical industry	<p>Strong external competition and high proportion of the import of finished products</p> <p>Need for cooperation and professional networks among micro- and small-sized enterprises in the sector</p> <p>Negative attitudes towards odors and pollution during biomass processing and waste disposal</p> <p>Heterogeneity of raw materials, low share of separate collection of waste</p>	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: Bulgaria
BG	Financial barriers	Low access to finance and low level of interaction in public-private funds and investments	Expert opinion
BG	Food industry	<p>emerging problems of: raw material securing; competitive pressure from the traditionally highly developed European market; constantly growing and increasing requirements and standards for quality and safety; strong pressure from commercial chains for market access; growing need to implement new technologies and solutions; addressing the problem of providing specialists and technologists.</p> <p>Insufficient raw material base in many of the sectors and lack of qualified labour; Relatively small technical capacities and insufficient administrative capacity, which make it difficult to participate in operational programs;</p> <p>Insufficiently developed technologies for food production, lack of potential in enterprises for innovative implementations;</p> <p>Weak awareness and commitment to the problem of food loss and waste so separate collection and use of food waste is not implemented.</p>	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: Bulgaria
BG	Fragmentation and lack of collaboration	The bioeconomy sector in Greece is still fragmented, with limited collaboration among different actors, such as academia, industry, and government. This can hinder the development of a holistic and integrated approach to bioeconomy.	Expert opinion

BG	Governance & policy	<p>Agricultural Academy provides expert support to the National bioeconomy strategy through various BIOEAST initiative activities, including national TWG and various platforms (farmers, forest owners, entrepreneurs, NGOs) designed to strengthen synergies between sectors.</p> <p>Need of business innovation by upgrading competences of science, technology and innovation (STI) public sector policy makers along with guidelines and mechanisms promoting socially just and sustainable use of raw materials for the bioeconomy. Integration with farmers and other processors for sustainable supply of raw materials and capturing economies of scale</p>	D1.4. BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
BG	Socio-economic	<p>Depopulation of small areas Lack of population in villages which are produce and collect biomass long term</p>	Expert opinion
BG	Technological	Development of technologies for obtaining bio-based, recyclable and degradable products	Expert opinion
BG	Value added agriculture Aromatic plants - essential oils	<p>Cultivation of aromatic plants outside of their traditional areas in the country, due to the expanding biomass (flower) production volumes _ planting material with unclear variety origin and authenticity. Processing and valorisation of by-products and agro-wastes generated _ low level of industrial scale application of new extraction technologies as a base for diversification of the generated products.</p> <p>Long term horizontal cooperation between farms growing oil-bearing plants and distillation facilities</p> <p>Weak links and cooperation between R&D organizations and the industry _ industry dominated by SMEs with low capacity for testing of innovations and technologies at a semi-industrial and industrial scale and low potential for their effective insertion into the production chain.</p>	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: Bulgaria
BG	Wood & furniture	<p>Changes in technology and potential applications of new nanomaterials in the furniture industry include the production of lighter, stronger and more durable materials; replacement of dangerous fire-resistant materials with new ones; application of new gluing techniques; introduction of new functionalities of the materials, etc.</p> <p>Need for efficient management to intensify use of information technology and electronic commerce for developed marketing as well as administrative capacity, to make it possible to participate in operational programs</p> <p>Development of research and development activity to fill the gap of partnerships with research organizations to technologies for extraction and processing of wood and processing of waste and by-products by turning them into bio-based components, fertilizers and energy</p>	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: Bulgaria
CZ	barriers	legislative, financial and administrative barriers have been identified as the main current barriers	Expert opinion

CZ	barriers	legislative, financial and administrative barriers have been identified as the main current barriers	Expert opinion
CZ	Climate challenge	An important challenges is planning for climate change action. The major threat for the country in near future is the lack of planning the circular and sustainable valorisation of the available bioresources. Another important aspects is the cross-sectorial approach which can improve cooperation in the production and processing of bioresources.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Czech Republic, page 4
CZ	Crop breeding	One of the main challenges is crop breeding that can withstand climate change, achieve sustainable yields and to provide the right nutrition.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Czech Republic, page 11
CZ	Decarbonisation	Another challenges is streaming bioenergy towards decarbonisation of National Economies. Decarbonization presents the country with many challenges. Czech Republic has a lot of forest-related territory. The use of biomass can be reduce gas emission and contribute to the country's decarbonization.	BIOEAST STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA, page 62
CZ	motivation	there is a need to introduce bioeconomic strategy tools that would lead to motivation within the bioeconomy	Expert opinion
EE	Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increase the value added of resources produced in agriculture (especially cereals, raw milk and currently unused biodegradable waste, residues and by-products) both by increasing processing capacity and by new technological solutions (e.g., biotechnological applications). - monitor the development of the livestock sector, affected by changes in consumption preferences and also by the need to limit the GHG emissions. - agricultural land use change due to the potential decline of the livestock sector, grassland biomass will become unused. - ensuring biodiversity and functioning of ecosystems, and adaptation to climate change. 	Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
EE	bioenergy	cascading use of biomass, creator of high added value from new solutions for the industrial processing of biomass, where those by-products and residues unnecessary for industrial use are used for energy. Residues, waste and by-products of biological origin, especially manure from agriculture, would find a more important use in the production of biogas and bio-methane	Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
EE	Fisheries / aquaculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • make better use of the existing fish resources. • development of cultivation technologies for macroalgae and sea shells and to finding additional possibilities for economic use, which are currently underutilized and which help to remove biogenic substances from the sea and reduce the eutrophication of the Baltic Sea. 	Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper

EE	Governance & policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ongoing activity on strategic documents : Roadmap for green transition in agriculture and food expected to be published • lack of comprehensive planning and cooperation in circular bioeconomy at the local community and industry • Consumer awareness of the environmental impact of their choices and bio-based alternatives with low environmental impact is also low. 	Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
EE	Innovation Research & Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • modest ability of the business sector to spend on R&D activities limits the introduction of new technologies and product development. • not enough attention is paid to the transfer of knowledge about the circular bioeconomy, R&D and innovation. • lack of specialists who can relate existing bioresources to different processing methods, bioproducts and opportunities in the value chains. • Bioeconomy related research groups are fragmented, with an uneven level. Cooperation between research groups and entrepreneurs needs improvement. <p>2022: Roadmap for RDI was prepared that also covers the bioeconomy needs</p>	Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
EE	wood industry	The share of export of paper wood as a raw material is also high, as cellulose and paper are produced in limited quantities in Estonia, and the more modern methods of refining, such as chemical refining are not widespread. However, products that add value to sawmill production, such as wooden factory houses, carpentry and joinery products, furniture and furniture parts are highlighted in current and future exports.	Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
GR	Lack of connection between administration, business and science	Enhancing cooperation and mobility between the public, private sector and scientific institutions will help researchers and heads of research organizations to identify issues of common interest to them and businesses	Expert opinion
GR	Energy efficiency Prioritization	Lack of connection between the topic of energy efficiency and energy crisis and bioeconomy activities, research and investment	Expert opinion
GR	Lack of investment and funding	One of the most significant challenges for implementing a bioeconomy in Greece is the lack of funding and investment, which is crucial for building the necessary infrastructure and supporting research and development.	Expert opinion

GR	Regulatory and legal barriers	The existing regulatory and legal frameworks in Greece may not be supportive of the bioeconomy, and can be seen as a barrier to the growth and development of the sector.	Expert opinion
HR	Agriculture	Agriculture biomass flow indicates three origins of biomass in Croatia: crop production, grazing and residues. Data on the unused or unknown uses of biomass indicate around 78% of agricultural residues are not being utilised, with 6% of generated food waste from total feed and food production. There are also unknown losses of 35% of the total biomass supply _ land productivity gaps	concept paper for bioeconomy strategy: Croatia, section 3
HR	bio-energy/forestry	Agriculture biomass is used at a very low level for bioenergy purposes, only 0,01% of the total biomass supply. The available woody biomass to boost novel value chains in the bioeconomy are waste and by-stream from the wood processing industry, which makes representatives from that sector incumbent bioeconomy players in Croatia.	concept paper for bioeconomy strategy: Croatia, section 3
HR	Food industry	abundance of biomass as a total, the farm_to_fork sector would be in focus for the transition to circular and sustainable bioeconomy by using the existing biomass more efficiently__ low labor productivity. high quality potential that could climb at the top of the bioeconomy pyramid: pharma and cosmetics industry. However, the stakeholders in the survey indicate that this potential is not recognised _ The untapped potential for improving product functionalities and adding value with technologically advanced biobased solutions is recognized in Croatia's 'novel' manufacturing sectors as the most relevant	concept paper for bioeconomy strategy: Croatia, section 3
HR	Governance & policy	Assembling of the multidisciplinary working group by the coordinating actor. The group include members of different ministries, incl. ministries of Science and Education; Economy and Sustainable Development; relevant faculties, research institutes, public sector stakeholders. Need for an inter-ministerial working group, involvement of the local level, sectoral organisations and research	D1.4. BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
HR	Innovation	Patent applications in 2015-2019 Croatia ranked on the lower end of patent applications among the BIOEAST countries. The highest position (4th place) was taken in food chemistry field with 1 application per million inhabitants. Factors that had a negative impact on innovation, including insufficient early stage financing (first and second round of investment), tax incentives, and the business environment (uncertain and low market demand)	p.98 D 4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST

HR	Research & Development	seldom initiatives of science-business cooperation in bioeconomy-related R&I that could serve to foster R&I activities _ Insufficient public-private partnership between academia, public and the private sector in most of bioeconomy sectors _ Low cooperation with foreign partners among innovative enterprises in Croatia's fully and partly bio-based industries _ low share of national funding for bioeconomy-related R&I except for pharmaceutical industry	D 4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST
HU	Action plans	In the draft (not public) HU bioeconomy Strategy, there is a lack of action plan, in terms for actual steps.	Expert opinion
HU	biomass production_forestry	interest for Hungary to maintain support for afforestation climate change in the Carpathian Basin causes significant damage to the forest population. Rapid changes can upset the ecological balance of our native tree stands. Because of decline in the growth of trees and decrease in the amount of timber less renewable raw materials will be available. Huge unprocessed biomass leaves the country and return in the form of value added product.	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: The Hungarian Path
HU	biorefineries	(i) Hungary is heavily dependent on imports of natural gas from areas hit by geopolitical conflicts. (e.g. Ukrainian war) It has highlighted the risks of dependence on fossil fuels. (ii) The biofuel sector has a huge corn potential need. In times of drought, problems can arise in supply chains. (iii) Without systemic thinking the energy crisis may generate huge damages in biomass potential (iv) The recovery of organic by-products and wastes is a poorly organised and underdeveloped.	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: The Hungarian Path
HU	failed investment in the past	previous bioeconomy investment measures (within the rural development programme) have failed so far as they were not profitable enough.	Expert opinion
HU	food system	(i) Household biological waste recycling and generating valuable materials from (ii) Global crises and geopolitical conflicts may generate problems in food / feed security. The domestic food industry is still struggling with efficiency problems.	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: The Hungarian Path
HU	Food waste not processed	lack of action to take advantage of food waste. Some stakeholders have identified food waste as the most useful biomass source.	Expert opinion

HU	Gap in research and investment	Investment gap from private sector when it comes to projects with "middle" TRL (TRL 3-6) . Businesses usually get involve din either low TRL level project 1-3). Small SMEs are not supported	Expert opinion
HU	governance, policy	Submission of strategy to the government and public consultation for building up a national action plan during 2021. Operational coordination to achieve in the context of inter-ministerial working group led by the Ministry, stakeholder working groups, EU projects (e.g. Power4bio), Bioeconomy Cluster.	D1.4. BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
HU	knowledge, innovation	The shortage of talent and skill has limited the innovative activity of Hungarian enterprises. Cooperation among researchers and businesses is weak, hindering knowledge transfer from abroad, and towards smaller domestic enterprises. Strengthening the research and innovation capacity of domestic firms and training professionals could secure long-term growth and competitiveness	Bioeast foresight report
HU	lack of biomass uptake	There is no need for more biomass production, Hungary has one of the highest biomass quantity and diversity, but processing and linking to bioeconomy activities is missing	Expert opinion
HU	Lack of cooperation	Cooperation between different stakeholder groups/actors is not at a satisfactory level.	Expert opinion
HU	Lack of focus on bioeconomy policy development	Due to the development of the CAP strategy, which was a priority for the Ministry's administration	Expert opinion
HU	lack of funding	From the Ministry perspective there is a lack of funding	Expert opinion
HU	Lack of interactions among stakeholders	the different bioeconomy actors are not fully aware of what everybody is doing, especially when it comes to project implementation and research	Expert opinion
HU	Lack of involvement of young people	From the Ministry perspective young people are not interested in the bioeconomy topic	Expert opinion
HU	private sector absence	Lack of presence of the private sector, energy companies, energy providers as well.	Expert opinion
HU	resources: soil & biodiversity	Due to the increased rate of biomass extraction, soil organic matter stocks have declined. Global warming and the increasing water demand would potentially result in water shortage, which threaten the present ecological status of waters and biodiversity.	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: The Hungarian Path
LT	Agriculture scale	The declining scale of agriculture in the country, especially livestock farming, may adversely affect the potential of a raw material suitable for biogas production.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 11

LT	Application in circular economy	Low level of application of the circularity principle, in particular for the production of higher value added products from manure, slurry, other plant and animal waste	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 9
LT	Cooperation and clustering	Undeveloped economic cooperation and clustering in bioeconomy sectors	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 9
LT	Demography	Decline in working age population in Lithuania (both in cities and rural areas).	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 9
LT	Efficient biomass use	New and more efficient biomass use is relevant transformation pathway in Lithuanian agriculture, the manufacture of food products and beverages, manufacture of textiles, wearing apparel and leather, manufacture of wood and wood products, pharmaceutical products sector, and sector of renewable energy.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 7
LT	Labour skills	Disturbances in training of specialists and skilled workers for bioeconomy sectors.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 9
LT	Primary sector productivity	Boosting primary sector productivity is very relevant transformation pathway in Lithuanian textiles, wearing apparel and leather sector and the manufacture of wood and wood products.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 7
LT	Technology transfer level potential	Low level of scientific research commercialization.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 9
LT	Valorisation of ecosystem services	Valorisation of Ecosystem services is relevant pathway in all primary production and other bioeconomy related sectors (renewable energy, organic waste management, and green care, nature tourism and recreation)	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 7

LV	Agriculture	<p>development opportunities in the agricultural sector proposed in LIBRA is mainly connected to efficient land use:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increased land-use efficiency by extracting more value added per hectare of agricultural land; • bringing into production around 400,000 hectares of land utilised for agriculture that is currently unused; • by extracting more added value from grassland currently maintained in good agricultural condition but not used for the production of high-quality natural products, by using it more efficiently. 	Latvian Bioeconomy Strategy (LIBRA) in vigor since 2018
LV	Fisheries / aquaculture	<p>Due to the degradation specialised fishing for cod in the Baltic Sea from 2020 has been prohibited. Aquaculture development projects in previous years have introduced fish species such as Arctic char, trout, shrimps, as well as investments in modernisation and development through the purchase of fixed assets has been made. Existing fish ponds have been restored and hatcheries developed</p>	Latvian Bioeconomy Strategy Concept paper
LV	forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Half of Latvia's forest areas are state-owned, resulting in slower decision-making and possible politicisation of decisions; • Depend almost entirely on public funding for research; • Mostly only primary resources are used; • Secondary bioresources are used as energy wood or exported; • Shortage of skilled labour; • CO2 is not stored in products with a long lifetime. At the moment, the use of wood resources is focused on short-lived products such as energy pellets; • No up-to-date data on forest stock, inventory only every 20 years; • Land use change from agricultural land to forest land is complicated. Time-consuming and costly to change land use; • Lack of a developed market for the use of secondary and tertiary resources in higher value-added products 	Latvian Bioeconomy Strategy Concept paper

LV	Governance & policy	<p>In the Latvian Bioeconomy Strategy 2030 main challenges related to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – innovative, risk mitigating technologies for growing plants and breeding animals – sustainable and productive growing under the conditions of climate change; – development of innovative niche products with high added value – technological solutions for the bio-based activities by the scientific and industrial communities in the country. <p>Of the 15 clusters officially recognized by the Latvian government, 6 share bioeconomy interests: Latvian high added value and healthy food cluster, Life Science Cluster of Latvia, Latvian wood construction cluster, Food products quality cluster, Clean Technology Cluster, Green-Tech Cluster.</p>	<p>4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST</p>
LV	Innovation Research & Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latvia's lowest indicators in 2020 are in R&D investment, the share of innovative small and medium-sized enterprises; • slow and fragmented development of technology transfer and innovation system hinders the growth of productivity, and production and export of products with high added value in bioeconomy sectors. Of the 8 competence centres established under the Government measure “Support between Competences Centres for the Development of New Products and Technologies”, are operating in the bioeconomy field. 	<p>4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST</p>
LV	wood industry	<p>commercialise innovative products :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • textile from wood (foreseeable future- innovation in downstream sectors to replace widely used, unsustainable or fossil-based products) • particle board, a product already on the market with high demand and a wide range of applications, whose environmental performance could be improved in line with the principles of sustainability and the circular bioeconomy • natural thermal packaging - innovative product, which could enter the market in the coming years 	<p>Latvian Bioeconomy Strategy Concept paper</p>

PL	Agriculture / forestry	<p>Conventional bioeconomy sectors in Poland include agriculture and forestry, as biomass production sectors, and those with the food-industry, which all constitute the most important part of the Polish Bioeconomy, thus they are representing the main challenge in the sustainable transition. The productivity of farms in Poland is one of the lowest in the EU as a result of agrarian fragmentation, as well as lower soil quality and a shorter growing season than in Western European countries. In such a situation, the need to reduce the use of mineral fertilisers and plant protection products is linked to the need to implement technological progress and improve knowledge and skills in the biomass production and food/feed processing sector</p>	<p>Bioeconomy Concent Paper Poland, page 7</p>
PL	Balance /nature/ climate / economy	<p>One of the main challenges is to find a balance between sustainability and economic development. Balance should be based on relationship between nature, climate and economy. One of the most important elements is to create synergistic new knowledge based on new science, but we can't forget about traditional, so we should find the right balance.</p>	<p>BIOEAST FORESIGHT EXERCISE Sustainable Bioeconomies towards 2050, page 108 (This is general for all BIOEAST countries, but applied to Poland as well)</p>
PL	Biogas and biomethane sector	<p>Development of the biogas and biomethane sector with high potential for the management of integrated supply chains in agriculture (by-products) and food industry as a crucial sector for energy independence to exploit waste that requires the following measures: (1) stabilization of the economic and legal context for biogas and biomethane producers; (2) promotion of sustainable business models of biogas plants for waste management and for agriculture as a necessary element for recycling of waste biomass to maintain soil fertility; (3) support for modern technical solutions, including flexible demand driven meso and micro installations.</p>	<p>Bioeconomy Concent Paper Poland, page 8</p>

PL	Biomass use / waste stream recycling	<p>Another transformation pathway that should be pointed out with respect to the bioeconomy growth in Poland, relates to the innovation in downstream sectors, which increase the efficiency of biomass use and waste stream recycling. New and more efficient use of biomass streams through the cascading use is gaining new meaning in the bioeconomy, especially in primary sectors (agriculture, forestry) and 'conventional' manufacturing sectors (wood and wood products, in particular). Among novel bioeconomy sectors, the sector of chemicals and chemical products stands out as the most relevant, according to the survey results. In those sectors, survey respondents recognized the most relevant potential of this transformation pathway. There are several factors however, that need to be efficiently tackled before the potentials of this transformation pathway is exploited. The first challenge is inter-sectoral cooperation (let alone integration) among bioeconomy sectors, which is rather low, resulting in broken, incomplete value chains. Next challenge, which is just adding from previous one, are challenges, associated with the establishment of biorefineries (already tackled previously in BIOEAST.EU/BIOEASTSUP Page 129 of 359 these conclusions). the impact depends on supply dynamics, consumer behaviour and the regulatory environment</p>	BIOEASTsUP Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy Institutional profiles - comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 128
PL	Collaboration	Despite existing initiatives and partnerships, there is a further need to strengthen cross-sectoral, private and public-private cooperation, e.g. to reach new markets, joint investments and implement initiatives for mutual benefit.	Expert opinion
PL	Consumers and Producers motivation and incentives	Producers and consumers do not always want to use products or intermediates with higher added value. In a cascade system, if a cheaper alternative exists - it is chosen as a cheaper substitute.	Expert opinion
PL	Crop structure	In the case of Poland one of the main challenges for the establishment of efficient logistic flows is a scattered and small-scale land ownership structure in Poland. Taking into account the fact that biomass sources are relatively heterogeneous, this makes the organizing of cost-efficient provision of biomass at the industrial scale a great difficulty.	BIOEASTsup Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy institutional profiles - comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 63

PL	Governance and connectivity	In this area, we can note the following barriers in Poland: - Fragmentation of the political framework - Lack of interministerial and cross-sectorial coordination, - Lack of national bioeconomy AND circular economy strategies, - Lack of political willingness and trust in institutions, - Unclear roles and guidelines, - Low connectivity and public-private partnerships.	BIOEAST FORESIGHT EXERCISE Sustainable Bioeconomies towards 2050, page 107 (This is general for all BIOEAST countries, but applied to Poland as well)
PL	Guaranteeing sustainability and security of biomass supply in the long term	It is necessary to develop resource-based models to ensure a continuous supply of biomass for e.g. the biogas or biomethane sector, but also for the development of innovative bio-solutions or bioproducts.	Expert opinion
PL	Industry AND Workforce	Another challenges are related to 'Industry AND Workforce' area. We can point out to challenges: (1) Jobs are lacking in the high-value levels of the CBE, (2) Loss of workforce and manpower to other countries.	BIOEAST FORESIGHT EXERCISE Sustainable Bioeconomies towards 2050, page 108 (This is general for all BIOEAST countries, but applied to Poland as well)
PL	Inland aquaculture	Development of the inland aquaculture in Poland requires: (1) creating conditions for developing new business models for products with high added value; (2) creating support systems for fish farms, which will include a fee for ecosystem services provided by the sector, especially for water management and water retention, providing habitats for many valuable species and places for recreation; (3) establishing local partnerships of science, business and administration for strengthening cooperation within the sector and for educational purposes; (4) promoting products of inland fisheries as products with high added value and low carbon footprint.	Bioeconomy Concent Paper Poland, page 9
PL	Knowledge	The next challenges is lacking of knowledge. We can show several fields: - insufficient awareness of the bioeconomy as a concept; - cross-sectorial knowledge difficulty; - invalid/out of date education of farmers; - unclear vision and understanding by policy-makers; - lack of indicators, robust and appropriate data.	BIOEAST FORESIGHT EXERCISE Sustainable Bioeconomies towards 2050, page 108 (This is general for all BIOEAST countries, but applied to Poland as well)

PL	Lack of knowledge/skills/competencies	Innovative approaches are still lacking within some bioeconomy sectors. A linear model of thinking operates. There is a need to move to new mental maps. There is often a lack of collaboration with R&D departments and sometimes a lack of specific knowledge, skills or competences to manage related operations.	Expert opinion
PL	Lack of market demand for bio-based products	might sometimes require the creation of new market segments	Expert opinion
PL	Lack of promotion and wide-use of adequate technology (e.g. In biogas sector great technology is not widely used)	There are many technologies on the market, often available on a smaller scale, that need the development of appropriate business models as well as promotion. Such an approach will contribute to a faster development of the bioeconomy in Poland.	Expert opinion
PL	Lack of public/consumer awareness	As mentioned above, there is a lack of awareness on both the consumer and producer side about the lack of consequences of moving to, for instance, clean energy or reducing the impact on climate change. An additional aspect is the lack of perception of the efficient use of biomass.	Expert opinion
PL	Maintaining uniform products and by-products.	Poland has one of the largest and most developed agri-food sectors in Europe. This is linked to the high volume of biowaste produced. This represents a huge potential for the development of the biogas or biomethane sector. However, it is difficult to ensure a flow of biosources of similar composition and mix, which may pose difficulties in maintaining product homogeneity.	Expert opinion
PL	Need for investment to integrate and adapt biorefineries	There is certainly a lack of biorefineries, particularly those located in rural areas, which, with effective partnerships, could create new jobs and could also contribute to more sustainable, higher value-added chains.	Expert opinion

PL	Organic farming sector	Development of the organic farming sector as a niche sector in Poland, which, in the future, is to significantly increase its impact on the economy, should include: (1) increasing the number of producers and consumers of organic farming products; (2) changing the perception of consumers in assessing the value of organic farming products as high value added products; (3) increasing technical capabilities of organic farming and the availability of knowledge and dissemination of information on organic farming in Poland; (4) increasing the possibility of interaction between producers and consumers in order to boost consumer involvement in the sustainable development of organic farming	Bioeconomy Concent Paper Poland, page 8
PL	Price competitiveness	It is difficult to compete in markets with cheaper products, also with imported products e.g. From China.	Expert opinion
PL	Quality or efficiency of final products	Products from biomass development may be perceived as lower quality than those from fossil resources. This is the case with the perception of fuels. The challenge is to influence mindsets and adapt to change.	Expert opinion
PL	Resources / technology	Another challenges is lacking of resources and technology. We can show several fields: - unused biomass potential; - lack of biorefineries; - lack of dedicated funding and additional funding sources; - low productivity and added value; - addressing climate change; - resource efficiency; - water management.	BIOEAST FORESIGHT EXERCISE Sustainable Bioeconomies towards 2050, page 107 (This is general for all BIOEAST countries, but applied to Poland as well)
PL	The need to scale-up bio-solutions	There are many interesting bio-solutions that are prototypes or exist on a small scale. There is a need to support such solutions, through the implementation of innovative business models, promotion, enabling development.	Expert opinion
PL	There are legal barriers to bioeconomy development	Despite the many initiatives and projects taking place, policy makers have still not developed a strategy for the development of the bioeconomy. The development of some sectors is being hampered, e.g. the first biomethane plant in Poland is about to be built and there are no legal regulations for its grid connection.	Expert opinion

RO	a pronounced agrarian profile and predominantly rural regions	agricultural sector characterized by low productivity + ageing population + low degree of openness to innovation and requalification + significant decrease in the population employed in agriculture	Expert opinion
RO	Balance /nature/ climate / economy	One of the main challenges is to find a balance between sustainability and economic development. Balance should be based on relationship between nature, climate and economy. One of the most important elements is to create synergistic new knowledge based on new science, but we can't forget about traditional, so we should find the right balance.	BIOEAST FORESIGHT EXERCISE Sustainable Bioeconomies towards 2050, page 108
RO	Biomass use / waste stream recycling	Another transformation pathway that should be pointed out with respect to the bioeconomy growth in Poland, relates to the innovation in downstream sectors, which increase the efficiency of biomass use and waste stream recycling. New and more efficient use of biomass streams through the cascading use is gaining new meaning in the bioeconomy, especially in primary sectors (agriculture, forestry) and 'conventional' manufacturing sectors (wood and wood products, in particular). Among novel bioeconomy sectors, the sector of chemicals and chemical products stands out as the most relevant, according to the survey results. In those sectors, survey respondents recognized the most relevant potential of this transformation pathway. There are several factors however, that need to be efficiently tackled before the potentials of this transformation pathway is exploited. The first challenge is inter-sectoral cooperation (let alone integration) among bioeconomy sectors, which is rather low, resulting in broken, incomplete value chains. Next challenge, which is just adding from previous one, are challenges, associated with the establishment of biorefineries (already tackled previously in BIOEAST.EU/BIOEASTSUP Page 129 of 359 these conclusions). the impact depends on supply dynamics, consumer behaviour and the regulatory environment	BIOEASTsUP Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy Institutional profiles - comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 128
RO	Biorefineries	One of the challenges is scale of biorefineries. Many regions in the country were don't have any biorefineries. In some local realities small-scale biorefineries are better solution than large-scale biorefineries, which is why policy-makers should build solutions corresponding to the context.	BIOEAST FORESIGHT EXERCISE Sustainable Bioeconomies towards 2050, page 110

RO	Crop structure	In the case of Romania one of the main challenges for the establishment of efficient logistic flows is a scattered and small-scale land ownership structure in Romania. Taking into account the fact that biomass sources are relatively heterogeneous, this makes the organizing of cost-efficient provision of biomass at the industrial scale a great difficulty.	BIOEASTsup Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy institutional profiles - comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 63
RO	Freshwater based bioeconomy	Fresh water is very important for Romania, but most of the region's water bodies are in less than good condition. This may be due to increasing economic development and amount of various pollutants. The region urgently needs to mitigate the impact of climate change on ecosystems, improve water management of rainwater and development of drought management plans.	Strategic research and innovation agenda summary, page 16
RO	Governance / connectivity	The next challenges is lacking of good governance and connectivity. A common case is unclear roles and guidelines, low connectivity and public-private partnerships. Another case is lack of political willingness and trust in institutions, lack of national bioeconomy and circulareconomy strategies, fragmentation of the political framework and the last problem is lack of interministerial and cross-sectorial coordination.	BIOEAST FORESIGHT EXERCISE Sustainable Bioeconomies towards 2050, page 110
RO	governance of the BE	defining the roles in developing the BE at national level: creating the vision, defining priorities, responsibilities	Expert opinion
RO	Insufficient awareness about the concept in general	Only few actors are aware of the concept (mostly RDI and innovation actors) or entities involved in research projects (clusters, SMEs in cooperation with RDI/Universities), innovation voucher schemes etc....	Expert opinion
RO	lack of awareness about the potential of the BE sectors		Expert opinion
RO	limited financing opportunities	mainly dedicated to research (collaboration of academia with companies) or for RDI infrastructure	Expert opinion
RO	low innovation capacity		Expert opinion

RO	System of organic farming	Based on the experts' and the stakeholders' opinions, the system of organic farming has been recognised as one of the promising niche sectors in Romania for the development of country's bioeconomy. Even if organic agriculture has registered a sinuous development, the general trend is upward, the potential is huge, the development of ecological agriculture being driven, for the most part, by the financial support granted through the CAP.	Bioeconomy Concent Paper Romania
RS	Wood waste	Even though there is a high potential of using it as biomass a lot of wood waste is left in the forest after cuttings. There is a need for investments, subsidies and technology transfer in forestry sector.	Expert opinion
RS	Knowledge gap	Most potential stakeholders (from ordinary people to ministries) have not heard of the term bioeconomy. They have heard of the concept of circular economy, which is defined in different frameworks, but they are not familiar with the details.	Expert opinion
RS	Lack in funding	High initial level of investment required for the implementation of BE principles and lack or low-level of subsidies and non-repayable funding for companies that participate in BE.	Expert opinion
RS	Lack of good practice examples	There are almost no examples of good practice at the national level, which would much better demonstrate the importance and possibilities of BE in Serbia compared to international examples.	Expert opinion
RS	Lack of infrastructure and capacities	Deeply rooted technologies of linear production. Lack of procedures and structures enabling a redesign of a technological process to prevent the consumption of unnecessary resources, professional personnel in the field of BE, tools for BE management ...	Expert opinion
RS	Lack of understanding from key stakeholders	Within current governmental organization term/obligation/duty for BE is not delegated non of ministries/institutions/agencies and as such is not recognized by our government while initiative for circular economy are present	Expert opinion

RS	Legal barriers	Non-recognition of bioeconomy concept in laws and sectoral policies. Governmental delegated duty for BE is not present. Currently institutions do not recognize BE in their agenda	Expert opinion
RS	Limited awareness and education	The Greek population has limited awareness and education on bioeconomy, which can hinder its adoption and development. Education and awareness-raising campaigns are necessary to inform and involve the public in bioeconomy efforts.	Expert opinion
SI	Adoption of strategies and action plans	Slovenia currently has zero circular or bioeconomy strategies or action plans. The government is very hesitant to make decisions in regards to sustainability as every decision usually receives heavy backlash from certain part of the stakeholder ecosystem and with strong lobbies, it can lead to early elections. Circular bioeconomy and sustainability in general is therefore in a standstill, resulting in companies and other organisations being confused as to what they can invest in as the country has no clear guidance on where it wants to be in the future.	Expert opinion
SI	Agricultural and forest-wood biomass	One of the most important challenges in Slovenia is raw material potential of agricultural and forest-wood biomass which is significant, but sub optimally utilized . One of the problem with it is the structure with is fragmented and produces large amounts of side streams and residues.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 11
SI	Creation of governmental push	The government needs to step up and create either a policy push or more stringent criteria for companies to get access to state funding.	Expert opinion
SI	Decarbonisation	One of the challenges is streaming bioenergy towards decarbonisation of National Economies. Decarbonization presents the country with many challenges. Slovenia has a lot of forest-related territory. The use of biomass can be reduce gas emission and contribute to the country's decarbonization.	BIOEAST STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA, page 62
SI	Innovation / B+R	Innovation in Slovenia is a major challenge, as there is no such trend in the country. Investments in RDI and publishing are being intensively developed. Slovenia also compares favourably in terms of the number of startups, which is growing steadily, which may suggest an entrepreneurial shift to the bioeconomy.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 11

SI	Institutional status	Also the institutional status of bioeconomy remains poorly defined. No ministry or other government body can be described as an institutional holder of the bioeconomy portfolio. The level of coordination between instruments and measures supporting various aspects and sectors of bioeconomy remains low.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 6
SI	Integration / enterprises	The next challenges in Slovenia is a low level of horizontal and vertical integration along the bioeconomy value chains. The main issue is the low level of integration and cooperation of enterprises in the bioeconomy sectors. By this fact, most enterprises operate on the scale of SMEs.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 11
SI	Lack of funding	There is enough funding in the EU circular bioeconomy ecosystem but not enough budgeting for sustainable technologies is being done internally in companies.	Expert opinion
SI	Lack of knowledge	There is a severe lack of knowledge in companies regarding circularity, accelerating bioeconomy and sustainability. The ecosystem lacks supportive actors, consultants and technology experts. There is a huge technology know how gap. There are little to no engineers equipped with the knowledge of implementing modern technologies.	Expert opinion
SI	Lack of management motivation	The management in Slovenia is not pushed by anyone currently to start implementing sustainability or accelerating circular bioeconomy.	Expert opinion
SI	Legal barriers	Slovenia is currently heavily prioritising nature conservation which is completely fine. But sometimes the legislation goes a bit too far in terms of prohibiting certain applications that would be beneficial for the acceleration of bioeconomy in the nation. For instance biochar is currently still not accepted as a fertiliser that is beneficial for agriculture, waste sludge from bio-based industries cannot be applied to agricultural fields even if treated properly.	Expert opinion
SI	Productivity and performance of primary sectors	Factor productivity and economic performance of primary bioeconomy sectors (agriculture in particular), is below par with the rest of the national economy, as well as in macro-regional comparison with other BIOEAST countries.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 6

SI	Synergies	Synergies between (advanced and internationally integrated, but transient) industry and RDI sector in the domain of bioeconomy remain largely untapped.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 6
SK	Decarbonisation	One of the challenges is streaming bioenergy towards decarbonisation of National Economies. Decarbonization presents the country with many challenges. Slovakia has a lot of forest-related territory. The use of biomass can be reduce gas emission and contribute to the country's decarbonization.	BIOEAST STRATEGIC RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA, page 62
SK	Evidence-based policy making	In the case of system changes the policy commitment is a paramount factor affecting the bioeconomy deployment. In this area attention and efforts are needed mainly in improvement of knowledge and data for evidence-based policy making, implementation of the EU policies related to bioeconomy and circular economy (Bioeconomy Strategy, Green Deal, Farm2Fork, new soil legislative, Fitfor55, etc), and also in preparation of an effective Road map for circular bioeconomy (currently under preparation) and its effective implementation.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovak Republic, page 9
SK	Implementation of the existing strategies	Several strategical documents have been developed, however their practical implementation is lagging behind	Expert opinion
SK	Inter-sectoral dialogue	Changes require also new or updated forms of governance and cooperation, so establishment of the inter-ministerial and inter-sectorial dialogue to promote synergies among different supporting tools and policies, such as Strategic plan CAP 2023+, cohesion funds in Operational program Slovakia, Resilience and recovery plan and other policies dedicated to support of all stakeholders dealing with research, innovation, development of entrepreneurship with special attention to SMEs, including the access to finance and venture capital have to be in the top areas of interest of policy makers.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovak Republic, page 9
SK	Lack of funding	Lack of funding at national level; necessity to motivate private investments	Expert opinion
SK	Lack of inter-institutional cooperation	Lacking cross-sectoral and inter-ministerial collaboration	Expert opinion
SK	Legal barriers	Without sound legal framework, it is difficult to implement bioeconomy solutions	Expert opinion
SK	Low level of awareness, adding value through bioeconomy	Educational system does not reflect current needs; education at all levels is necessary. Low general perception of bioeconomy does not force companies to apply relevant principles, unless they bring immediate profit	Expert opinion
SK	Unstable political situation	Often changes at high-level positions (ministers, directors general, directors); early elections in September 2023	Expert opinion

7.5 Potentials

Reported potentials sorted by key words and country

Country	Key words	Short description	Reference
BG	Agriculture	Possibilities for the use of biomass from abandoned (uncultivable) lands	Expert opinion
BG	Biochemical industry	The chemical industry belongs to the "novel" bioeconomy-related sectors with development opportunities for a traditionally leading sector in the manufacture and export of chemical products, phosphorus and nitrogen fertilizers and medicinal products. Foreign companies have invested in the big Bulgarian chemical plants along with a great number of small enterprises established, especially in the sector of plastics and rubber products and also in recycling industry. Active knowledge and innovation transfer in big enterprises and well-developed conventional production of chemicals, fertilizers, plastics, plastic products, wares and packaging, allowing rapid transition to the bio-based production. Availability of scientific potential in the field of biomass production and processing in bio-fertilizers, bio-based cosmetics, biopolymers, etc. through international collaboration in R&D Adaptation and implementation of EU regulations on the green transformation of the chemical industry	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: Bulgaria
BG	Bio-waste	Converting biological waste and residues into valuable resources and creating innovation and incentives	Expert opinion
BG	Encourage collaboration and copying	using good practices to improve collaboration between administration, business, and science	Expert opinion

BG	Food industry	<p>The food-taste industry (FTI), including the three major sub-sectors "Food", "Beverages" and "Tobacco products" is traditionally one of the most highly developed branches in the Bulgarian industry. The established production links with other industries and its contribution to the stability and development of the national economy are an indication of its economic importance.</p> <p>The increasing interest in the consumption of biologically pure and healthy foods by Bulgarian consumers necessitates the production and market realization of such products.</p> <p>Rapidly developing technologies for processing food waste and by-products and turning them into bio-based components, fertilizers, chemicals, energy, and availability of good European practices for reducing food loss and waste; Numerous innovations in food production and orientation towards the production of medicinal, dietary and functional foods with high added value;</p>	<p>Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: Bulgaria</p>
BG	Governance & Policy	<p>MAFF coordinates the development of a National bioeconomy strategy and integrates the bioeconomy in the CAP Strategic Plan National Strategy for Development of Scientific Research Coordination of S3 update/revision : MOEW coordinates national circular economy activities in which the concerned ministries participate (MAFF, ME, MES, MRDPW) _ Available sectoral and national strategies with focus to the circular bioeconomy</p> <p>Active public participation in identifying problems related to the storage and processing of chemical products and waste</p>	<p>D1.4. BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS</p>
BG	Great potential from forest biomass	Forests occupy 38% of the area of Bulgaria	Expert opinion

BG	Value added agriculture Aromatic plants - essential oils	The cultivation of aromatic plants and essential oils production is a traditional industry for Bulgaria, as the country is one of the world largest producer and exporters of rose (<i>Rosa damascena</i>) and lavender (<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>) oils, in total more than 55 kha have been cultivated (MAF 2022). Well-established technologies & sufficient capacity of the distillation facilities and organic solvent extraction Sectoral cooperation active & enforced legislation for organic farming Scientific potential and research infrastructure for complex research _ Innovations and technologies tested at the laboratory level available _ established international collaborations and recognition in R&D	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: Bulgaria
BG	Wood & furniture	1,500 enterprises representing the "Woodworking" sector and 1,700 enterprises representing the "Furniture industry" sector distributed in different regions. It covers about 2% of the industrial production and also creates about 2% of the added value in the industry. The index of industrial production and turnover in the sector improved by 6.4 and 3.6 points, and foreign trade amounts to about 1.5% of the country's total exports and 1% of the country's total imports. Personnel costs in Bulgaria as a share of production are smaller compared to similar ones in the EU for woodworking and furniture production, an important advantage in a labour intensive sector. A renewable technological park with a high degree of implementation of modern machines; Support from a strong branch organization	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: Bulgaria
CZ	Biotechnology / Education	Important sectors of the bioeconomy potential are biotechnology and breeding, composting and biogas, education in bioeconomy. Biotechnology sectors are very important for bioeconomy strategy in the Czech Republic, as 27% of total bioeconomy turnover came from biotechnology-based industries.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Czech Republic, page 8, 11
CZ	Food industry	We can see the huge potential of the bioeconomy in the food sector, as 43 % of the total turnover into the organic economy comes from the food industry.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Czech Republic, page 8

CZ	Industry/ renewables/	A visible element of the bioeconomy potential in the Czech republic is renewable sources that are replacing fossil fuels. Other important aspects of the bioeconomy's potential are: modernize primary sector, improve resource efficiency, develop industrial applications, comprehensive approaches to value chains, consumption, and ecosystem services.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Czech Republic, page 11
CZ	innovation, production	in general, we believe that the bioeconomy has great potential in the Czech Republic	Expert opinion
EE	Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Among the 37 PRODCOM products that generate 50% of the total value of the recorded products, 24 are bio-based product or fossil based that can be changed to bio-based. They make 25% of the total value (mostly from wood industry and secondly the livestock sector) • perspectives for agroecology and regenerative agriculture, agroforestry, wetland agriculture, sustainable aquaculture and fisheries, and sequestration of “blue” carbon. • digestate is a valuable material for circular bioeconomy that has a positive effect on maintaining and increasing the nutrient and carbon content of the soil. Enriching the fermentation residue with bio-based and also fossil (e.g., oil shale ash) substances makes it possible to further increase the positive effects on soils. 	D 1.2 ANALYSIS OF BIOEAST NATIONAL BIOECONOMY SECTORS Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
EE	Governance & Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • activity on strategic documents in 2022 <p>2022 Jan: Ministry of Rural Affairs submitted and the Government of the Republic of Estonia approved cabinet memorandum about bioeconomy development</p> <p>2022 Apr: Expert committee of the green policy steering committee of the Government of the Republic of Estonia published ‘green policy report’ that touched briefly also circular and bioeconomy issues.</p> <p>2022: White paper of circular economy was approved.</p> <p>In November-December 2022 the ministries prepared responses/action plans to the ‘green policy report’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • extensive clustering in biogas production, dairy sector, arable crops, horticulture, beef cattle, organic farming, woodhouses, waste recycling 	D1.4. BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS BIOEASTsUP congress presentation

<p>EE</p>	<p>Innovation Research & Development</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging cooperation models and networks (enterprise cooperation, cooperation between enterprises and the state, international partners and research groups) • Supporting participation in international networks and consortia for using EU research and innovation • Supporting investments for testing, piloting and technology scaling infrastructure (including offshore) and respective centres. • Development and introduction of small technological solutions suitable for community and regional levels. • Adaptation and application of the best practices and technologies of circular bioeconomy in Estonian conditions. • Application of IT solutions, including artificial intelligence, the creation of digital cooperation platforms, optimization of processes and increased efficiency. • Improving the central access to state-ordered (applied) research and data in the Estonian Science Information System; communicating the possibilities of the system outside the academic circles. 	<p>Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper</p>
<p>EE</p>	<p>wood industry</p>	<p>In timber sector, Estonia is an exporter of wooden houses. Cooperation within the Estonian Woodhouse Association (https://www.puitmajaliit.ee/en) helps to develop this sector further. Also, one of the largest wood pellets producers in the EU, Graanul Invest Ltd. develops wood chemistry. Currently they are executing the EU Flagship project Sweetwoods. The value chain of wood is currently based on the mechanical processing of wood and is centred around sawmills, wood pellets and heating materials production. Approximately 50% of the handled wood is used for heating.</p>	<p>Estonia Bioecon Strategy Concept paper</p>

EE	bioenergy	<p>• Estonia is the least energy dependent among the EU-27 with an increasing trend and it achieved the mandated share of energy from renewable sources by 2020. In terms of bioenergy, the state of the art of Estonia is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bioelectricity: 124 GWh primary production of biogas and 1.223 GWh of electricity from solid biofuels • Biofuels for transport: 20.5 ktoe of total consumption from biofuels in transport (4.9 ktoe bioethanol, 12.3 ktoe biodiesel and 3.3 ktoe from biogas) • Solid biomass: 18.608 GWh from solid biomass primary energy production and 11.630 GWh from solid biomass gross inland consumption <p>During the 2010-2017 period, Estonia was showing the highest growth in liquid biofuels industry compared to other BIOEAST countries</p>	<p>D 1.2 ANALYSIS OF BIOEAST NATIONAL BIOECONOMY SECTORS 4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST</p>
GR	Abundance of natural resources	Greece has an abundance of natural resources, including agricultural products, forests, and marine resources, which can be used as feedstocks for bio-based products and energy.	Expert opinion
GR	Existing infrastructure and expertise	Greece has existing infrastructure and expertise in areas such as agriculture, food processing, and chemical industry, which can be leveraged for the development of the bioeconomy.	Expert opinion
GR	Growing demand for sustainable products	There is a growing demand for sustainable products and services worldwide, which can create opportunities for Greek businesses to tap into this market by developing innovative bio-based products and solutions.	Expert opinion
GR	Strategic location	Greece's strategic location can be an advantage for accessing European and international markets for bio-based products and services.	Expert opinion
HR	Agriculture	In 2020, the gross added value of primary agricultural activities amounted to HRK 12.1 billion, which represents about 3.9% of the Croatian economy. Although this share is decreasing, the primary sector has had significant economic multipliers in other related industries in the last two decades.	concept paper for bioeconomy strategy: Croatia, section 3

HR	bio-energy/forestry	in the forestry sector, where renewable energy gain as same synergy strength as the wood processing industry. secondary biomass from sustainable forest management has been already contracted at the existing and pending solid biomass cogeneration plants for the next 5 to 14 years.	concept paper for bioeconomy strategy: Croatia, section 3
HR	Food industry	The food production sector is concentrated in a small number of large players with the top 10 companies accounting for 44% of the total revenue generated in 2015 (World Bank, 2016f). Large companies hold significant shares in production capacity throughout the Western Balkans and are increasingly making strong inroads into emerging markets.	concept paper for bioeconomy strategy: Croatia, section 3
HR	Governance & Policy	Preparation of the National Bioeconomy programme is officially launched in April 2021: comprehensive assessment of the governance structure, innovation facilitating instruments, and key innovation assets – research and human capital – strong monitoring and evaluation (M&E) framework of five priority sectors of the economy and their innovation potential (food and bioeconomy among them). Main actor: Ministry of Agriculture (coordination) Participation of several ministries (Economy and entrepreneurship, Science and education, Environment and energy, Regional development, See, transport and infrastructure, Tourism), public research institutes and sectoral organisations. Platforms/Networks: BIOEAST; BBI-JU platform; smart specialization strategy, international research, SCAR, IEA Bioenergy Task 43	D1.4. BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS D 4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST
HR	Innovation	In terms of all types of innovation activities, Croatia was significantly lower than in Innovation leader countries in most of reported fully and partly bio-based industries, except for the manufacture of pharmaceuticals, chemicals as well as the manufacture of rubber and plastic	D 4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST
HR	Research & Development	biobased activities large share of GVA _Prominent scientists and large number of R&D institutions _ innovative enterprises in manufacture of pharmaceuticals, chemicals, rubber, plastics and	D 4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE

		furniture_ ICT companies and infrastructure plus Dynamic growth of ICT application in all business processes	BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST
HU	Action Plan discussions	Point of discussion for the workshops, at the Co-creation (3rd workshop series) in order to include in the CEE2ACT roadmap for Hungary, a clear set of actions	Expert opinion
HU	biomass production_forestry	(i) Biological properties (deep and extensive roots, foliage) of woody plants are able to produce large amounts of organic matter. (ii) Classic ecosystem services provided by forests, such as climate change mitigation and adaptation, hydrological, services, support to agricultural productivity, reduced erosion, increased wildlife habitat and wood or other forest products availability may help decrease geopolitical tensions and maintain the health of the population.	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: The Hungarian Path
HU	biorefineries	Feasibility of the mobile biorefinery concept has already been demonstrated for the processing of green biomass (e.g., grasses) to produce proteins for feed and fibre fractions for soil enhancers or for producing biogas. Another project aimed the partial processing of algae to obtain proteins, fats, and carbohydrate components for food, feed, and fuel production. The trend may accelerate regarding currently ongoing (i) transition to climate neutral energy production and (ii) defossilisation of industries like textile, plastics, pharmaceutical sector, energy sector etc.	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: The Hungarian Path
HU	Capacity building and interconnection between the research and investors	In the 1st workshop	Expert opinion
HU	capacity building on bioeconomy funding	Again, capacity building on bioeconomy funding should be included in all workshop series, solid opportunities, for example, that a project proposal derives from these meetings	Expert opinion

HU	Capacity building on how to apply for funds, topic to be included in the workshop series	learning from CEE2ACT contributing countries, how they are applying for funds,	Expert opinion
HU	energy investment efficiency	CEE2ACT will stimulate discussions around the energy efficiency topic and facilitate connections between relevant actors	Expert opinion
HU	food system	(i) Biological waste can be a valuable feedstock in case of biorefineries (ii) By diversification of the raw material base and changing eating habits making diet more healthy (iv) Rethinking sustainable production methods (v) To overcome the efficiency problems in food industry, we find the spread of industrial digitalisation to be the right tool.	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: The Hungarian Path
HU	food waste topic inclusion	Additional topic to be discussed during workshop series	Expert opinion
HU	governance, policy	Main actor: Ministry of Agriculture (bioeconomy); Ministry of Innovation and Technology (circular economy, where biomass is one of the pillars); Ministry of Interior (wastewater management); Ministry of Human Resources (higher education). Platforms/networks: BIOEAST, RDI office, applied research, Chamber of Agriculture, universities and institutes, professional associations	D1.4. BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
HU	knowledge, innovation	obstacles for acceleration of a knowledge-based bioeconomy Hungary's innovation performance is moderate below the EU average Hungary still belongs to assembly countries by its position in the global value chains It has dominant backward participation with using foreign inputs in exports than supply intermediate goods and services that are further used in other countries' exports (forward participation).	Bioeast foresight report
HU	networking events	CEE2ACT to organize more than 1 workshop series but networking events	Expert opinion
HU	Policy screening exercise	Explore ways of supporting a cross-sectoral "screening exercise" to find links between the EU CAP, bioeconomy and other policies, strategies, actions plans to see what is	Expert opinion

		prioritized in other countries/what should be prioritized in Hungary.	
HU	resources: soil & biodiversity	(i) Adequate organic matter potential can be achieved in two ways: by leaving a significant part of the formed primary biomass on the ground, or by returning secondary/tertiary biomass (e.g. compost, organic fertilizers) to soils. (ii) It is also essential to restore degraded soils and to rehabilitate degraded areas, such as disused industrial areas, agricultural sites, railway areas, making such areas suitable for the resumption of biomass formation, specifically where it is appropriate for production purposes.	Bioeconomy Strategy Concept Paper: The Hungarian Path
HU	Stakeholder mapping, exploration of needs	Within activities of CEE2ACT in WP3 there is the stakeholder mapping. The Ministry is interested to see the involvement of local stakeholders, farmers, and mostly with the local mayors. And the government's task to develop local solutions for the energy crisis. At the Ministry they are trying to work with local energy communities to tackle the energy crisis.	Expert opinion
HU	Young people involvement	widening bioeconomy network among young people	Expert opinion
LT	Biogas infrastructure	The country's biogas production equipment industry is growing, providing biogas power plants and biogas purification (biomethane production) equipment to the market	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 11
LT	Biomass availability	Biomass availability is relevant asset in the sectors of agriculture and forestry. Biomass availability in Lithuania represents the most important and relevant asset for the development of bioeconomy	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 7
LT	Biopower Cluster	A Biopower Plants Development Cluster operates in the country, uniting business, agricultural sector companies, research, and study institutions for the development of biomethane production technologies and the dissemination of information in society	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 11
LT	Business consolidation	The level of business consolidation is the most relevant in the manufacture of pharmaceuticals in Lithuania	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT

			PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 8
LT	Circular technological solutions and business models	Emerging industrial initiatives that actively develop circular bioeconomy technological solutions and business models, for bio-based transformations are very relevant in the manufacture of pharmaceuticals and relevant in the sectors of agriculture, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture, the manufacture of food products and beverages, manufacture of wood and wood products, construction sector, renewable energy sector, and organic waste management sector.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 8
LT	Demand for biological materials consumption	Rapid growth of biological materials consumption in the country's economy	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 9
LT	Policy	EU (and Lithuanian) policy on food waste reduction and strategic decisions on its use in biogas production.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 11
LT	Policy commitment and availability of public funding	Policy commitment and availability of public funding for supporting bioeconomy-oriented projects is a relevant asset in agriculture and the manufacture of wood and wood products in Lithuania	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 8
LT	Social partnerships	Strengthening social partnerships in Lithuania's rural areas	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 9
LT	Strong 'conventional' bioeconomy-related industries	The presence of strong 'conventional' bioeconomy-related industries is a relevant asset in the manufacturing sector of wood and wood products.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 8
LT	The efficiency of infrastructure/logistics	The efficiency of infrastructure/logistics is relevant asset in the sectors of agriculture, manufacture of wood and wood products, and renewable energy sector.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY OF THE STRATEGIC CONCEPT PAPER FOR BIOECONOMY: LITHUANIA - p. 7
LV	Agriculture	The primary biomass production sector, i.e. agriculture, forestry, fishing and aquaculture contributes to 36% of the Latvia's bioeconomy turnover. The value of primary production per hectare of agricultural land in Latvia is one of the lowest in the EU. In addition to the strengths of the Latvian	Latvian Bioecon Strategy Concept paper

		<p>forest sector, research institutions and companies operating in the industry have over the years accumulated a strong knowledge and skills base, which needs to be redirected from the conventional bioeconomy towards a sustainable, innovative, and knowledge-based one.</p>		
LV	Fisheries / aquaculture	<p>The fisheries sector in Latvia is divided into three main spheres of activity: fishing, fish processing and aquaculture fish (sprat, herring, cod, flounder, etc.) caught in the Baltic Sea and in the Gulf of Riga, over the years the amount of fishes caught has had a decreasing tendency - main species (herring, salmon, flounder, salmon, cod) decreased, except for sprat, and other species.</p>	Latvian	Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
LV	forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest biomass is one of Latvia's most valuable bioresources, already providing financial, socio-economic, and environmental benefits to the Latvian state • The Latvian state is the largest owner of forest land therefore, the national state itself has enormous potential to implement and enforce a coherent forest management strategy, while seeking the best ways to develop the sector and products, so it can influence the development of the forest sector; • Forest resources (timber) are recognised as a key resource in regional and national policy planning documents; • Over the years, knowledge and experience about forests and forest management have been accumulated; • Universities with accumulated knowledge carrying out research on the forest sector; • The mild climate ensures a diversity of tree species; • Developed infrastructure for wood-processing enterprises; export infrastructure by land and sea; • Forest as a national cultural treasure • the manufacture of wood products and bio-based furniture, food, beverages and tobacco and agriculture are largest bioeconomy turnover generators, altogether generating about 80% of the overall bioeconomy turnover. In Latvia, the wood products and bio-based furniture sector being the main contributor, almost a third (32.6%) of overall bioeconomy 	Latvian	Bioecon Strategy Concept paper

		turnover comes from the forest-based industry.	
LV	Governance & Policy	responsible for the bioeconomy is the Ministry of Agriculture, which is also responsible for the forest sector interacting with other state and state-owned entities related to the forest sector. It is advised on forestry-related issues by the Forest Advisory Council, that brings together various potential interest groups - representatives of private, state and municipal forest owners and managers, timber industry, non-wood forest value managers, forest management service providers, environmental and nature protection, as well as labour interest groups. Ministry is also a state shareholder in joint-stock companies LSF and Ltd “Latvian Rural Advisory and Training Centre Forest Advisory Service Centre” providing clients with access to knowledge, advice and other services related to the sector	Latvian Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
LV	Innovation Research & Development	Increasing collaboration on innovation shows year by year increasing number of research projects, establishment of clusters and competence centres. Several EU-funded research projects using biomass feedstock and biotechnologies have been running in Latvia in the last few years. This demonstrates the interest and commitment for the bio-based activities by the scientific and industrial communities in the country.	4.2 STATE OF-THE-ART INNOVATION GAPS AND NEEDS OF THE BIOECONOMY RELATED R&I IN THE BIOEAST

LV	wood industry	Latvian biomass flows indicate a dominance of wood-based biomass with high share of export in a shape of solid wood products, roundwood and wooden pellets. The contribution of the forest-based bioeconomy (Forestry, Manufacture of wood and wooden furniture, Manufacture of paper and paper products) accounted for 51% of the value added and 38% of the bioeconomy employment.	D 1.2 ANALYSIS OF BIOEAST NATIONAL BIOECONOMY SECTORS Latvian Bioecon Strategy Concept paper
PL	Agriculture / forestry	The conventional bioeconomy sectors require regional planning coordination towards: - the review of production technologies to increase their productivity: including the exploitation of marginal and abandoned land, reducing the use of natural resources and increasing the use of biobased fertilizers; - reconsidering the biomass value-chains by overarching systemic management of agricultural biomass to fully exploit its economic potential for both food and non-food use, i.e. food and non-food valorisation should be connected by promoting the interconnection of production and processing sectors of the bioeconomy (including production of biomaterials, biomethane, etc.); - developing monitoring systems to monitor the carbon footprint of processes and products; - strengthening the relationship between the main sub-sectors of the food sector, the biogas and biomethane sectors, and the production of bioproducts and bio-based carbon as well.	Bioeconomy Centent Paper Poland, page 7-8
PL	Bio-based transofrmation	However, despite the fact that emerging industrial initiatives for bio-based transformation, such as smart specialisations, KETs or clusters, have been in place for many years, there is still a untapped potential for development in Poland. There are only few clusters oriented on the development of the bioeconomy. Beside that there is no strategy for KETs (Key Enabling Technology) at the national level in Poland, which is not being a very innovative EU country.	p. 272; DELIVERABLE 1.4: BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
PL	Biomass - supply side	Poland has a high potential of biomass on the supply side from "conventional" manufacturing and organic waste management sectors for the development of new and more efficient use of biomass streams. The primary sectors are assessed similarly. The survey study found that	p. 273; DELIVERABLE 1.4: BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING

		supply-side sectors in Poland have untapped potential to provide biomass to demand-side sectors.	AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
PL	Existing best practices within each bioeconomy sector	Some economic activities in the bioeconomy operate in a traditional manner (e.g. aquaculture). On the other hand, there are very well-functioning entities from the business environment within the sectors in question that can set an example for alternative players.	Expert opinion
PL	Geographical location	Poland, due to its geographic location, has great potential for the transfer of biomass and bioproducts, also in terms of providing storage space.	Expert opinion
PL	High potential and biomass resources from agricultural and forestry production	This is a quantitative and qualitative potential. Poland is at the leading position in the European Union countries with the largest utilised agriculture area (4) and in terms of the number of farms (2) [Eurostat]. Likewise for the forestry sector, it is one of the European Union countries: with the largest area (hectares) of wooded land (8) and growing stock (thousands cubic metres) of forests (3).	p. 271; DELIVERABLE 1.4: BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
PL	High potential for promoting quality food products	Poland has quality food, which is not promoted adequately. One of the most developed agri-food sectors in the EU. Slightly promoted and known food products (compared to Italy or Spain).	Expert opinion
PL	Insufficient level of innovation in the bioeconomy	Poland has untapped potential to introduce and develop innovative solutions in the bioeconomy. Compared to other countries, considering the rankings and statistics, Poland has a lot of work to do to raise the level of innovation.	Expert opinion
PL	Large residual biomass potential	Being a country whose agri-food industry is a key sector of the economy and one of the largest in Europe, Poland has a large residual biomass potential. Organic residues are used in the domestic production of biogas or biofuels. While the availability of biomass from primary sectors or production processes is strong asset, its logistics are challenging. This is the result of the structure of the farms, the short time needed to deliver the residual biomass and the storage time	p. 271; DELIVERABLE 1.4: BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

PL	Low labor productivity	According to Smędzik-Ambroży et. al (2019) it has been evaluated that agriculture in Poland, compared to other EU countries, was characterized in the years 2004-2017, almost by the lowest level of resource productivity.	p. 272; DELIVERABLE 1.4: BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
PL	Novel sectors of manufacturing	The untapped potential for improving product functionalities and adding value can be observed in 'novel' manufacturing sectors, such as chemicals or plastics and rubber. The biomass share within mentioned so-called mixed bio-based 'novel' manufacturing sectors is very low (2.91 and 6.13 % respectively – Loizou et al. 2019).	p. 273; DELIVERABLE 1.4: BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
PL	Organic farming sector	In order to eliminate barriers to the development of the organic sector in Poland, it is necessary to: (1) increase the level of the institutional – non-financial support to farmers, through technological support, advisory services, market information; (2) support the market mechanisms aimed at the development of value chains. In order to reduce the risk of unfavourable changes, the following are needed: (1) farms that have stronger market power, (2) processors that will primarily focus on organic production, (3) strong market surveillance, also by the non-governmental organisations; (4) efficient network of knowledge dissemination; (5) efficient market information	Bioeconomy Concent Paper Poland, page 8
PL	Poland has a highly developed research infrastructure and human resources.	Within each bioeconomy sector, there is a developed R&D infrastructure and human resources within research and development centres that should contribute to the development of the bioeconomy. Combined with Technology Parks or business development agencies, they provide a solid base for the development of the bioeconomy. However, it is necessary to strengthen contacts and opportunities to exploit the potential for cooperation.	Expert opinion
PL	RDI sector	The RDI sector in Poland has definitely a high potential for development. 34.7% of companies operating in Poland were innovatively active in 2017-2019 . The share of innovative companies by company size is: 29.2% among micro enterprises,	p. 271; DELIVERABLE 1.4: BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING

		38.7% among small enterprises, 43.3% among medium enterprises and 56.7% among large enterprises. Polish companies more often introduce business process innovations (24.5%) than product innovations (13.1%)	AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
PL	Untapped potential for biomass processing	Poland has, in comparison to other countries, an untapped potential of its resources. Valuable and high-quality biomass is not processed locally, but sold/exported to other countries. Opportunities to increase the added value of biomass produced in Poland are not exploited.	Expert opinion
PL	Untapped potential of selected bioeconomy sectors	Given the resources at its disposal, and the example of other EU countries, organic farming, biogas and biomethane sectors have great potential for development	Expert opinion
PL	Untapped potential of selected bioeconomy sectors	Given the resources at its disposal, and the example of other EU countries, organic farming, biogas and biomethane sectors have great potential for development	Expert opinion
PL	Valorisation of bioeconomy sectors	The growing interest in valorisation of ecosystem services in recent times allows products and services that have a higher price to be valued more favourably. Although big effort is being made within few sectors in Poland, (e.g. organic agriculture, cultural and environmental tourism, labelling in food sector, waste management) there is still untapped potential in the majority of bioeconomy sectors.	p. 273; DELIVERABLE 1.4: BIOECONOMY INSTITUTIONAL PROFILES - COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, BENCHMARKING AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS
RO	Agricultural / organic farming	One of the most important sectors with bioeconomy potential in Romania is agricultural. One of the most important source of biomass in Romania is agricultural livestock and crop production. Romania has one of the largest agri-food industry sector in Europe. The potential in organic residues that can turn into biogas or biofuels is huge, but it is currently underutilized because one of the obstacle is logistics.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY ROMANIA, page 5

RO	Clusters promoting the concept and facilitating cooperation among actors, develop solutions		Expert opinion
RO	Natural resources / forestry residues	The next huge potential for the bioeconomy in Romania is the production of biofuels and biogas from natural resources and forestry, because they are not used in full.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY ROMANIA, page 5
RO	Organic products	Another important aspect of the potential of the bioeconomy is the development of the value chains for organic products. This is especially visible in small farms that use the limited chemicalization of primary sector.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY ROMANIA, page 5
RO	Potential in the sectors of food, agro, forestry, bioenergy	Potential in the sectors of food, agro, forestry, bioenergy	
RO	Potential in the sectors of food, agro, forestry, bioenergy	Potential in the sectors of food, agro, forestry, bioenergy	
RO	Potential in the sectors of food, agro, forestry, bioenergy		Expert opinion
RO	RDI / public support	RDI utilization is growing however it is still not at the highest level. More public support, funds, policy, collaboration, knowledge transfer and educations, and innovations are needed to improve this practice.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY ROMANIA, page 6
RS	Alignment of legal framework	Serbia is a candidate country in the accession process to the EU and therefore must adopt or align its legal framework to EU legislation and policies as a key component of the accession negotiations.	Expert opinion
RS	Existing circular economy networks	Current circular economy networks can be used for the promotion of BE concept and knowledge transfer.	Expert opinion

RS	Large agricultural and forestry area	This can provide a large amount of biomass available for inclusion in the circular BE process.	Expert opinion
RS	Large agricultural and forestry area	This can provide a large amount of biomass available for inclusion in the circular BE process.	
SI	Entrepreneurial projects	Slovenia has a vigorous network of enabling institutions supporting innovative and development-oriented entrepreneurial projects	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 9
SI	Lack of experts	As the educational system is not adapting to the changes in the world, there is a lack of industry experts for the sustainable transition. This is very apparent in the bioeconomy sector as well, where while working with them we saw that mostly there are no sustainability managers, circular experts etc.	Expert opinion
SI	Livestock excrements	Among the priority residual streams of agricultural biomass, livestock excrements were highlighted with a total amount of more than 620 thousand tons of dry matter. The overall performance of its current use (organic fertilizer) can be significantly improved by exploiting its energy content (biogas production) and improved soil fertilization techniques, which improves the nutritional value of livestock manure and drastically reduces environmental burdens.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 6
SI	Raw material potential	Slovenia has a significant but sub-optimally exploited raw material potential (in particular wood biomass and residues in primary agricultural production).	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 6
SI	RDI	In Slovenia, a vibrant RDI sector is operating, engaging in state-of-the art applied research and technology development in various bioeconomy-related fields of science. This sector, consisting of both, public research institutions and private companies, can play a stronger catalytic role in unlocking the bioeconomy potentials as it is currently the case. In some sectors, which can be regarded as the cornerstones of the national economy (e.g. pharmaceutical industry), RDI is strongly integrated with the industry.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 9

SI	Technology sectors	intensive	Apart from being the providers of biomass (often with poorly-valorised side-streams), integration with technology intensive sectors may act as a stimulus to improve their performance in several aspects (closing the material and energy loops, improved economic performance).	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 9
SI	Wood		With an exceptional forest cover (58 % of the country area are forests with a relatively strong production capacity), wood is by far the most promising source of raw materials in the Slovenian bioeconomy.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovenia, page 8
SK	Agroforestry systems		Another important potential of the bioeconomy in the Slovak Republic is agroforestry systems. Agroforestry systems are very important for environmental and can benefit the microclimate, water regime and biodiversity.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovak Republic, page 7
SK	Awareness / valorisation		Important factors in the development of the bioeconomy in Slovak Republic are low valorisation and processing in biomass production. Growing public awareness about Bioeconomy can be observed. Slovaks are focusing on sustainable solutions, land management, biomass use and healthy lifestyles.	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovak Republic, page 7
SK	Cars / mobility		Cars and mobility are an important potential for the bioeconomy in the manufacturing of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers, manufacturing of other transport equipment. It can help in implementation new progressive materials, products, technologies, fuels.	BIOEASTsUP Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy institutional profiles-comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 328-327
SK	Digital		Digital is a huge potential for the bioeconomy in the manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products, computer programming, consultancy and related services, information services. It can help with research, development and innovation of materials and technologies. It is important to support the digital transformation of all areas of society. It can help to improve the quality of life of citizens, increase the competitiveness of industry and the economy.	BIOEASTsUP Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy institutional profiles-comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 328-328
SK	Domestic resources	biomass	The dependence of the Slovak economy on imported resources and materials makes the economy vulnerable, while the potential for sustainable use of domestic resources remains untapped. Biomass	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovak Republic, page 5

		production is characterized by low valorisation and processing.	
SK	Healthy food / environmental	Healthy food is a huge potential for the bioeconomy in the crop and animal production, hunting and related service, and Forestry and logging. It can help in forest production, sustainable and competitive agriculture. It provides resources and services for society and the environment.	BIOEASTsUP Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy institutional profiles-comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 328-325
SK	Industry	Industry is a huge potential for the bioeconomy in the manufacturing of chemicals and chemical products, manufacturing of rubber and plastic products, production and processing of metals, manufacture of fabricated metal products, manufacture of electrical equipment, manufacture of machinery and equipment, electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply. It can help in implementation new technologies, environmentally friendly materials for industry, by-products, waste, progressive types of fertilizers, new progressive types of paper and leather. Innovative industry focuses on transforming industrial production to production-development.	BIOEASTsUP Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy institutional profiles-comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 328-326
SK	Interconnection of research and practice	Improving access to funding so that private actors can collaborate with research, academia and transfer scientific knowledge to practice.	Expert opinion
SK	Organic fertilizers	One of the main sectors that is growing bioeconomy potential is organic fertilizers production. A lot of biological waste can be transformed to biomass. In the Slovak Republic in 2022 created a platform of organic fertilizer manufacturers which name is " Association of Organic Fertilizer Producer"	BIOECONOMY CONCEPT PAPER EXECUTIVE SUMMARY Slovak Republic, page 5
SK	Public health / medical technology / health society	Public health is one of the potentials for the bioeconomy in Slovakia. The most important sectors where it can be used: biotechnology based products used in diagnosis and therapy, production of medicines, cosmetics, nutritional supplements, precise medicine, innovative products and technologies.	BIOEASTsUP Deliverable 1.4: Bioeconomy institutional profiles-comparative analysis, benchmarking and policy recommendations, page 328-329